

The Life Oasis International Church

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Language, Indo-European, Pidgin, Classical Indo-European, English-based pidgin, Germanic, Northwest Germanic, West Germanic, North Sea Germanic, Anglo-Frisian, Anglic, Later Anglic, Middle-Modern English, Macro-English, English, New Religiosity, Christian

The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church is among the thriving and prominent Pentecostal churches in Osun State, Nigeria. The church global headquarter is located in Osogbo the capital city of Osun State, Nigeria. The church is usually referred to as The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church. It was founded by Revered Olusola Ayodele Areogun who is also the current General Overseer of the church. The calling of the founder into the ministry can be dated back to as early as 1984 when he felt led to begin a missionary outreach in some rural area. The effort led to the planting of church known as Redemption Faith Churches. In this quest of fulfilling missionary mandate, great numbers of youth were raised and trained for the ministry. In the year 1988, Rev. Olusola Ayodele Areogun began a city-wide healing and victory campaigns with focus on teaching believers on how to obtain victory over sin, sickness and poverty. His bible teaching was so impactful that it drew both clergy and laity from different churches to his meetings. Another phase of his ministry began in the year 1989 when he officially began running of a church in Ilesa Osun State. However, in year 1996, Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun claimed to have received specific divine mandate from God. He said he stood with other ministers before the Lord and was asked to pick from the paper. In his own paper he found "committed to helping men realized their God-given dreams in life" With this divine mandate, his ministry has strategically focus on training, making disciple and helping people to realise their God's given vision. The Dream Centre of the life Oasis now has its international headquarters in km4 Gbongan Ibadan road Osogbo in Osun state. The church currently has branches in different parts of Nigeria. It has also extended her spread beyond Nigeria as there are branches across, UK, Europe and USA. The ministry has an online presence and a media outreach that rolls out various mediated messages on radio and television. One of their popular mediated messages on radio and television is called Living by the answer. The hosts are usually Rev Olusola Areogun and his wife, Rev Mrs Oyenike Areogun.

Date Range: 1988 CE - 2026 CE

Region: Nigeria, West Africa

Region tags: Africa, Nigeria

Nigeria, West Africa.

Entry Perspective

✓ Orthodoxy

Sources

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Sources

Academic (peer-reviewed) sources related to the subject matter:

ID:

Attach PDFs if available in digital format.

11403

- Source 1:: The Dream Centre of the life Oasis international church (2022)
- Source 2:: Ukah.A(2016) Megachurch Christianity Reconsidered
- Source 3:: Wallis. R(1984) The Elementary Forms of the New Religious Life

Media and third sector sources related to the subject matter:

ID: 11404

Attach PDFs if available in digital format.

- Source 1:: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church (2022)
- Source 2:: Sola Areogun Ministries (n.d) video channel
- Source 3:: Abundant Life House,(n.d) Books and media resources

List the top three most important religious texts for this religious movement

ID: 11405

Attach PDFs if available in digital format.

- Source 1:: Bible
- Source 2:: Bible
- Source 3:: Bible
- Other:: Daily devotion book (Spirit Meat Devotional)
- Source 1:: Bible
- Source 2:: Bible
- Source 3:: Bible
- Other:: Daily devotion book (Spirit Meat Devotional)

List the locations of any key archives relating to this movement

ID:

- List locations:: Online and physical location

11406

Notes: Telegram channel (DCNewsLiveUpdates) Online, Facebook @DreamCentreLOIC The Church
Headquarters location is Osogbo Nigeria Dream Centre HQ Km4, Gbongan Ibadan road near November 27
Interchange Osogbo, Osun State Nigeria

General Variables

Date Range

On what basis was the date range selected?

ID: 9727

- Founding period
- Decisive event

Notes: Life Oasis international church was a church born after the divine encounter of the founder. The church came after years of missionary involvement of the founder.

Religious Tradition

Is this entry focused on a transnational religious movement?

ID: 9728

Transnational - addressing an audience that transcends nation state identity or a particular ethnic/regional diasporic population

- Yes

Notes: Life Oasis international church has her main headquarter in Osogbo Osun State Nigeria . The church though has branches beyond the shores of Nigeria, and has global TV broadcasts and international attendees at their Oasis International Conferences.

Is this entry focused on a global religious movement?

ID: 9729

Global - addressing a particular ethnic or national diasporic identity that is dispersed globally

- No

Notes: The Nigerian context remains central to understanding Life Oasis, even though it has transnational aspects it is not global.

Is this entry focused on a specific national context of the religious movement?

ID: 9730

- Yes

Notes: Moreover, this entry focuses mainly on this national context of this religious movement within Nigeria

Regardless of scholarly classification, does the religious movement understand itself as part of a larger religious tradition?

ID: 9731

– Yes

Notes: Life Oasis is a Christian Faith base movement

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 9732

– Christian

Notes: The religious group, The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church is claimed to be a Christian group

↳ Is the religious movement a member of any overarching religious organisation or tradition? ID: 9733

– Yes Comment: The religious movement is part of christian faith tradition. It is however running her own independent Christian organisation

Notes: It is an independence religious organization

Does the religious movement engage in interfaith work? ID: 9734

– Yes

Notes: The church as a Faith base believes that until when Christ is formed in a man his service cannot be fully accepted by him

↳ Select all that apply

ID: 9735

- Interfaith dialogue sessions
- Interfaith humanitarian projects
- Interfaith religious services
- Interfaith educational programs
- Religious reconciliation initiatives
- Interfaith advocacy coalitions
- Shared sacred space initiatives
- Interfaith youth programs
- Interfaith chaplaincy services

State and Society

Is there violent conflict (within the geographical area under consideration)?

ID: 9737

– No

Notes: The church missionary headquarters is located in Osogbo, in Osun State. The city is an administrative and commercial nerve center of the state. The religious environment is pluralistic with the presence of Islam, Africa traditional religion or Yorel and Christianity . Notwithstanding there is relative peace amongst various adherent of religion within the area

Does the country have an official state religion or religions?

ID:

9738

– No

Notes: Life Oasis exist in Nigeria. The country does not have a state religion. It is considered as a secular state. The constitution of the country states that the nation shall be religiously neutral. However, the religious landscape of the land is diversified and shared among Christian, Muslim and African traditional religious adherent .

Is the religious movement's legal system the same as the country's legal system?

ID:

9742

– Yes

Notes: The life Oasis international Church is a legal religious movement. The constitution of Nigeria guarantee freedom of religion in the land in as much as the religious body obeys the law of the land. The church operates within the legal framework of the country. Nigerian constitution allows individuals and group to freely operate and practice religious activities as long as it obey the law of the country

Does the country have a secular government?

ID: 9743

A secular government maintains institutional separation between religion and state affairs.

– Yes

Notes: The country where life Oasis operates is Nigeria. The country operate democratic system of government. There is Federal system of government and the state is divided into 36 states. There is the executive arm of government , the legislative arm and the judicial arm of government. The country as a secular state does not support any religion

Does the religious movement maintain a separate legal system that operates alongside national law and addresses civil matters?

ID: 9744

– No

Notes: The church does not maintain any separate legal system . As a registered religious organization, the church operate under the law of the country which guarantee religious

freedom.

Is the religious movement formally recognised by the state ?

ID: 9745

This could be positive or negative recognition

– Yes

Notes: The church is recognized as a religious group and free to operate in Nigeria. It was registered under Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC) in Nigeria.

↳ Is the religious movement an officially registered religion?

ID: 9746

– Yes

Notes: It is registered officially

↳ Is the religious movement a charity/non-profit?

ID: 9747

– Yes

Notes: It is registered as a non-profit entity in Nigeria through Corporate Affairs Commission and functions as a charity and non-profit organization

↳ Is the religious movement a company?

ID: 9748

– No

Notes: The religious body is a non profit organization

↳ Is the religious movement considered a political religious movement?

ID:

– No

9749

Notes: Life Oasis International church is apolitical. The focus of the religious body is primarily religious.

↳ Is the religious movement considered a terrorist or proscribed organisation?

ID: 9750

– No

Notes: The religious body was never considered a terrorist organization or proscribed group. It is rather a registered and recognized non profit organization. The group has never been mentioned or linked with any proscribed group or any controversy. The church has rather continued to appear in positive light through their impact driven messages in the society

↳ Is the religious movement considered any other type of organisation?

ID: 9751

– No

Notes: The religious movement is not considered as any other kind of organization than church. However, it is registered as a non profit organization in the Corporate Affairs Commission in Nigeria.

Does the religious movement have official political support?

ID: 9752

– No

Notes: Amidst the political and religious landscape in Nigeria, the Life Oasis International Church has remain politically neutral and unaffiliated. The religious body is apolitical. It does not belong , support or have any affinity with any political group. of course this goes in line with many Nigerian Church practices who often maintain apolitical stance to preserve broad appeal in the society

Does the religious movement have social recognition as a 'religion' among the general population in this country?

ID: 9754

– Yes

Notes: The Church enjoys a social recognition as a christian ministry among Nigeria's general population, particularly in Osun State and in Pentecostal circle. Because of its activities, of which include church services, ministerial training, media programs, conferences, the church has a level of recognition among the christian populace. The church always draw crowd to the its headquarters base in Osogbo through its activities and program. The church runs both radio and television program on local radio stations, cable network and on online platforms, .

Does the religious movement have close affiliation with a political party?

ID: 9755

– No

Notes: The church does not have any affiliation with any political party. It apolitical in all of its operation

Does the religious movement actively discourage members from political participation ?

ID: 9757

Political participation includes voting, running for office, holding office and forms of political activism.

– No

Notes: The church does not engage in any political ideology. The church believes in building lives, making disciple through in-depth teaching of the bible.

Does the religious movement encourage its members to serve in the military? ID: 9762
– 0 Unclear views, neutral

Notes: The church is neutral on whether to join the military or not. Members are encouraged to work anywhere in as much as it is not illegal or a kind of work that will jeopardize their faith in God. Dignity of labor is encouraged in the church.

Does the religious movement broadly support nativism? ID: 9763
Nativism is a political ideology that favors the interests of native-born or established inhabitants over immigrants. In some cases, it entails the belief that immigrants are not legitimate members of the state.

– No

Notes: The church encourages her members to follow church tradition. It emphasizes building the body of Christ globally. It preaches inclusiveness rather than ethnicity or nationalistic teaching. The doctrinal stance of the church centers on Holy Spirit, Baptism, strong church government and preparing believers for service.

Does the religious movement teach that the national government should become more aligned with the religious movement's beliefs and practices? ID: 9765

– No

Notes: The teaching of the church encourages inclusiveness and integration into the body of Christ. It also promotes universal dream realization and kingdom advancement for individual. The church does not preach or teach cultural isolationism or a concept which seeks to make the national government to be coerced into aligning with its practices, rather the teaching of the group resonates with Nigeria's cosmopolitan charismatic scene rather than parochial nativism.

Does the religious movement teach that the current national government should be replaced? ID: 9771

– No

Notes: There is no such teaching which seeks to replace the current government in the group as the group is apolitical.

Does the religious movement describe itself as being persecuted or facing discrimination? ID: 9773

If answering for a particular national context, consider that context only. If answer for a globalized context, answer in the global context.

– No

Notes: The Life Oasis International Church does not describe itself as being persecuted in any form. The church is rather being commended by the government for the effort in building lives and making people to realize their dream

Has the religious movement experienced state-sanctioned violence?

ID: 9781

– No

Notes: The church has never experience any state sanctioned violence. as it has always align itself to the fundamental laws of the land

Is the religious movement viewed as having committed normative or legal violations? ID:

9783

– No

Notes: Life Oasis International Church is not viewed as having committed normative or legal violations. It has always maintain compliant operations as a non profit organization with active events and programming. There is no record or legal case against the church

Has the religious movement experienced state-sanctioned interventions?

ID: 9785

– No

Notes: The religious movement has not experienced a state-sanctioned intervention. It has faces no security or regulatory action. The church has continued to maintain its apolitical status and working within the routine of church activities amidst Nigeria broader challenges

Do members generally feel safe publicly identifying with the religious movement?

ID:

9786

– Yes

Notes: The members of Life Oasis International Church feel safe and publicly identifying with their church. In their public engagement with the public maybe during evangelism, they openly promote event like Web of Wisdom Conference, God of Breakthrough Conventions as well as sharing fliers to the public.. There has never been a report of fear, unnecessary persecution or assault on the members

Is there a derogatory term that people commonly use to describe the religious movement?

ID: 9787

– No

Notes: There is no derogatory term that people use to describe the religious movement. They are regarded as christian denomination

Is there a term that the movement uses for its members?

ID:
9789

– No

Notes: Life Oasis does not use any distinctive term for its members. Their identifier is "believer" "Saint " "Children of God". The church does not give any special appellation to the members.

Is there a term that the movement uses for non-members?

ID: 9790

– No

Notes: The church does not use any term for non members. In some cases they can be referred as friends , visitors. There is no specific language for them

Is there anything important about the relationship between the state and the religious movement that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly.

ID: 9791

– Specify: There is nothing else important about the relationship between the state and the religious movement that has not been covered.

Origins/Founder

When was the religious movement founded?

ID: 9792

– Write date or date range:: The religious movement was founded in the year 1989

Notes: In the year 1984, the founder Rev. Olusola Areogun was commissioned by God for a missionary work. His missionary activities included village outreaches and church planting. He continued in this assignment and planted churches under the name of Redemption Faith Churches. In the year 1988, he began a city wide healing campaign before it was formalized in the year 1989 when he received a mandate to begin a church

Primary language of the religious movement:

ID:
9793

Note to DRH team - Can this be less confusing to find the main linguistic groups in the world today than it was when Ted and I looked at it in April?

– Primary language: The primary language is English Language.

Notes: In Nigeria English language which is the national lingua franca is the official language of the movement. However, Yoruba language is seldom used to also communicate to the people, especially the local. The official language remains English. This is used for church services, teaching, and all of their publications

In which contemporary country was the religious movement founded?

ID:
9794

– Specify: The religious movement started in Ilesa, Osun State Nigeria

Notes: The church was located at coca cola area in ilesa. It was later relocated to the capital city of Osun state in Osogbo where the headquarters has remained. The church has now spread to other state in the country like Oyo, Ondo, Lagos, Kwara, Abuja, even it has branches in United Kingdom and in USA.

Write any historical or alternative names for the country:

ID: 9795

– Specify: Nigeria

Notes: Nigeria where the Life Oasis International Church was founded was historically known as the colony and protectorate of Nigeria during British colonial rule. Prior to the independence in 1960, the nation was comprised of protectorate of northern Nigeria, protectorate of southern Nigeria and colony of Lagos. These were amalgamated in the year 1914 under Lord Lugard. The name Nigeria was coined by Flora Shaw from the river Niger. During the colonial era, there were different regions. Some of them were Oyo Empire, Benin Kingdom, Sokoto Caliphate and various Igbo communities.

Are specific places important to the founding story of this religious movement?

ID:
9796

– Yes

Notes: Ilesa in Osun State where the church started laid the foundation of the religious movement. Life Oasis International Church is also referred to as the Dream Centre. The calling of the founder dated back to 1984 when he felt led by God to carry out specific assignment. The mission in the assignments are to show the world that Jesus is alive; and to teach believers how to operate the life of God in them. The assignment sparked the village outreaches which also led to the planting of churches under Redemption Faith Churches. In the year 1989, Rev. Olusola Areogun formally started a church in ilesa after a city wide healing services in 1988. However in the year 1996, Rev Olusola Areogun claimed to have had a specific mandate from God. He saw himself standing with other ministers of God. They were asked to pick from paper. In his own paper he found helping men to realize their God given dreams in life. This led to a shift in his assignment as he began to pursue the vision of helping people to pursue their dream. The church is now being referred to as the Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church

Is there an identifiable founder of the religious movement? (Answer more than once if multiple founders)

ID: 9797

– Yes

Name:

ID:
9798

– Write name: Olusola Ayodele Areogun

Notes: Was born into a polygamous family. He lost his father while still at a tender age. His mother Madam Maria Ajike Areogun raised e young Olusola and his siblings

↳ Birth Date: ID: 9799
– Write birth date:: He was born on May 12, 1962

↳ Sex: ID: 9800
– Male

↳ Primary language of founder: ID: 9801
– Write primary language:: Yoruba language
Notes: He speaks Yoruba language but his ministerial language is English.

↳ Ethnicity ID: 9802
– Write ethnicity:: Yoruba

Is there a symbolic or visual representation of the founder or founders? ID: 9803
– No
Notes: There is no symbol or visual representation of the founder or founders

Were the founder or founders part of an existing religious tradition? ID: 9804
– Yes
Notes: The founder of the Dream Centre of the life Oasis International Church is a Christian. The religious group he founded is also claimed to be a Christian denomination

Did the founder or founders claim direct communication with supernatural powers as a source of guidance for starting the religious movement? ID: 9805
– Yes
Notes: The founder Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun claimed to have received a mandate from the divine to teach believers about victory over sin and poverty. In his latter encounter with the divine in the year 1996, he claimed to have had a vision where he stood with other men of God and was instructed to pick from a basket. He found in his paper "helping men to realise their God given dream in life" . This has become the

mission of the group which now bears the Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church

Are the founder or founders considered to be human?

ID:

– Yes

9806

Notes: The founder Rev Olusola Areogun is considered as human with fatherly character. He is regarded as a minister who operate under special grace of helping men to fulfil their destiny in life

Are the founder or founders considered to be other or 'more' than human?

ID: 9807

– No

Notes: He is not considered to be more than human, rather he is regarded a man with special grace and as an oracle of God

Is the founder considered a prophet or divine intermediary?

ID:

– Yes

9809

Notes: Olusola Areogun even though does not bear the name or title as prophet yet every of his words and teachings are regarded to be emanating from the divine. He is also believed to be someone who speaks for God. His teachings are considered as truth explanation of the sacred text

Were the founder or founders believed to have spiritual or supernatural abilities?

ID: 9810

– Yes

Notes: The founder of the Dream Centre of Life Oasis International Church is believed by the followers to possess spiritual knowledge and abilities especially in revealing the mind of God as stated in their sacred text

Did the founder or founders prophesise about the future?

ID: 9811

– No

Notes: Though the founder does not engage in prediction or open prophesy yet he does engage in sacred text teaching of the future

Are the founder or founders considered infallible?

ID:

– No

9812

Notes: The followers does not consider the founder as infallible in principle but in action many of the followers exercise the trait

Are the founder or founders still alive?

ID:

– Yes

9813

↳ Does the founder or founders live in exile from their country of origin?

ID: 9814

– No

Notes: The founder of the Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church lives in the state of his origin and in the country . He is well respected in the community

↳ Has the founder or founders appointed successors?

ID: 9815

– No

Notes: The founder has not appointed a successor . Currently the religious group is being led by the founder and his wife

Are the founder or founders deceased?

ID: 9817

– No

Notes: The founder is alive and he currently leads the group with his wife

Do members value the founder's biography as sacred or as a source of religious knowledge?

ID: 9824

– No

Notes: The members does not value the founders biography either as sacred text or as a source of religious knowledge or authority. The members are taught through their sacred text bible, and they believed it as the source of their authority with the teaching of the founder believed to have been sourced from the bible

Sources of Authority and Texts

List the top three most important religious texts.

ID: 9825

Texts may or may not be written- they could be man-made objects, oral traditions or natural features - but are considered to be central to the recording and remembering of the religious movement's belief and/or practices.

– Source 1:: Bible

– Source 2:: Bible

– Source 3: The message of the founder and his teaching

Notes: The basic primary text for the members is the bible. Aside this, the members listen to the messages on tape and the books written by the founder

Have there been revisions to key religious texts?

ID: 9826

– No

Notes: There has never been any form of revision to their sacred text. They have continued to make use of the Bible as the basic teaching text

Are religious texts considered ancient by the religious movement (even if assessed differently by experts)?

ID: 9828

– No

Notes: The religious text among the members is never considered as just as an ancient text. It is rather accepted as the compass that guide all men to fulfilling their purpose on earth

Is there a believed origin of religious texts?

ID: 9829

– Yes

Notes: The religious text of the group is the Bible. It is a collection of 66 books which contain 39 books of the old testament and 27 books of new testament.

Select all that apply

ID:

9830

- Canonised
- Collective revelations
- Compilation of founder's teachings
- Divine revelations
- Oral tradition
- Prophetic visions
- Revealed
- Translated ancient texts

Notes: The origin of bible text is complex and it is multifaceted. It contains Old testament and new testament. The old testament was written between 1200-400 BCE. It was written primarily in Hebrew with some part written in Aramaic The new testament was written between 50-120

CE by the apostle, disciple and early leaders of the church

Is there a hierarchy of knowledge whereby deeper teachings are accessible only as members advance? ID: 9831

– No

Notes: The teaching of the group is accessible to all members . Every member has equal right to listen the founder

Are authoritative religious texts still being created? ID: 9832

– No

Notes: There are no other authoritative text beyond the teaching of the founder. All his teachings are recorded on tapes and are available for in both audio, video and in books. The founder himself lay claim to the authority of the bible in his teaching

Are some religious texts considered free from error (infallible and inerrant)? ID: 9834

– Yes

Notes: The group consider the bible as infallible and inerrancy. The founder does claim the authority of the bible as the final

Is there a formal process or institution for interpreting religious texts? ID: 9835

– Yes

Notes: There is an institution that focuses in ministerial training of which include interpreting religious text through bible study and teaching . There is an Annual School of Ministry called ASOM. It is a training hub to equip minister to realise their God's given dream

↳ Do members highly value the interpretation of religious texts by religious authorities? ID: 9836

– Yes

Notes: The members valued the interpretation of the religious text by the authority

Are individuals encouraged to interpret religious texts for themselves? ID: 9837

– Yes

Notes: Beyond the interpretation by the leaders, individual are also encouraged to learn more about the

religious text which is bible. This is done through in depth teaching of the bible by the leaders.

Are members encouraged to study texts or materials beyond those created by the religious movement? ID: 9838

– No

Notes: Members are encouraged to study the bible with others materials provided by the founder however they do not encouraged studying other materials from other source as they believed that the group have more than enough material to be studied than sourcing for materials elsewhere

Is direct personal experience valued as a source of religious knowledge? ID: 9839

– Yes

Notes: Personal experience is value as a key source of religious experience alongside with the scripture. This aligns with its Pentecostal root on spiritual encounter and divine revelation

Is channelled authority valued as a source of religious knowledge? ID: 9840

– Yes

Notes: Channelled authority is valued as a source of religious authority. This is through prophetic leadership and pastoral oversight. The founder claimed that he has a direct commission from God in 1984 to demonstrate Jesus life and was later given a vision to help men realised their dream. The teaching and ministrations of the founder serve as the authoritative channels, interpreting the Scripture via prophetic unctio and personal application

↳ Select all that apply ID: 9841

- Current leaders receive channelled knowledge
- Founder received channelled knowledge
- Individual members can receive channelled knowledge

Is 'scientific consensus' valued as a source of knowledge? ID: 9842

– No

Notes: The scientific is not consider as a source of spiritual knowledge. The teaching prioritize scripture, prophetic revelations personal spiritual experiences, channeled apostolic authority over empirical or scientific methodology

Does the religious movement take positions on empirical sciences such as biology, geology, and astronomy? ID: 9843

– No

Notes: The religious movement does not take position on empirical sciences either biology , geology or astronomy

Does this religious movement have a position on evolutionary theory? ID: 9845

– No

Notes: It does not take position or endorse evolutionary theory. The doctrine of the group prioritize literal biblical Creation account aligning with authority of the biblical story. The core belief affirm God as creator the bible is considers as infallible word of God and doctrine like Trinity is tied to Genesis creation story. The group also reject naturalistic explanation like evolution

Does the religious movement have beliefs that would generally be considered conspiracy thinking? ID: 9847

Conspiracy thinking refers to explanations for events which propose the existence of a conspiracy, containing knowledge contrary to current consensus.

– No

Notes: The group does not have any known belief that could be considered as conspiracy thinking. In the documented teaching and practices of the group, it focuses on biblical exposition, prophetic ministry, personal spiritual encounter and scriptural obedience than secular or speculative narrative. The core teaching centres on sovereignty of God. Creation story, salvation rough the finished work of Christ, equipping believers through pastoral leadership . Most of their sermon also engaged in addressing biblical and spiritual warfare

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement? ID: 9848
"Some truths are objective rather than relative."

– -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The religious group will strongly agree that some truth particularly biblical truth and doctrinal ones are more objective than relative. As the teaching of the group usually seek to uphold the scripture as infallible and unchanging standard for faith and practices. The teaching of the group uphold the biblical authority

Is there anything important about the texts of the religious movement that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 9849

– Specify: No

Notes: The religious text of the group is the bible

Media and Public Relations

Does the religious movement use print media?

ID: 9850

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 9851

- Books
- Fliers/pamphlets
- Magazines
- Newsletters
- Other:: It also uses digital media

Notes: There are many publications authored by the founder Rev Olusola Areogun. They are in different format covering print and digital media

↳ Does the religious movement have their own description of the purpose of their use of print media?

ID: 9852

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply:

ID:
9853

- Prayer request systems
- Proselytising/Recruitment
- Scripture
- Selfless service
- Sharing lifestyle advice
- Sharing testimonials
- Witnessing

Notes: The publications from the group covers various topic that relates to human

Does this religious movement use websites or blogs?

ID:

– Yes

9854

Notes: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church uses websites and blogs to share teaching, beliefs, service update on their platforms

↳ List the top three most important religious movement-run websites/blogs:

ID: 9855

– Source 1:: lifeoasisinternationalchurch.org

– Source 2:: solarwithministries.org/asom/

– Source 3:: [ijmtc.org/course/full-time a bibles school/](http://ijmtc.org/course/full-time-a-bibles-school/)

Does this religious movement use traditional broadcast media like telephone, radio or television?

ID:

– Yes

9856

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 9857

– Advertising on audio media

– Advertising on video media

– Audio recordings (e.g., record, cassette tape, DVD nonbroadcast recordings)

– Radio channels (run by the religious movement)

– Text messages (sent to telephone numbers and not through social media apps)

– Television appearances (on other people's channels)

– Television channels (run by the religious movement)

– Video recordings (e.g., VHS, DVD)

– Other:: Cable channels

Notes: These platforms are used essentially to preach and reach out to people .

↳ Does the religious movement have their own description of the purpose of their use of traditional media?

ID:

9858

– No

Notes: There is no specific official reasons spelt out for the use of traditional media. However the print media like books serves the purpose of training manual for equipping and making of disciples

Does the religious movement use social media ?

ID:
9860

Social media includes applications and platforms such as Discord, Facebook, Instagram, Kakaotalk, LINE, Telegram, Tiktok/Douyin, Wechat, Whatsapp, YouTube, X/Twitter, among others.

– Yes

Notes: The Dream centre of the life Oasis international church use social media

↳ List the main social media platforms this religious movement uses and estimate the size of their following on each (top three): ID: 9861

– Source 1:: Facebook 5.6k followers

– Source 2:: Instagram

– Source 3:: Youtube

↳ Does the religious movement have their own description of the purpose of their use of social media? ID: 9862

– No

Notes: There is no specific official description for their purpose in using social media. However their sermon, devotion and other important event are projected on the platform

↳ Do members often subscribe to movement-specific spiritual content or membership sites on social media? ID: 9864

– No

Notes: There is no evidence that members subscribe to the movement specific spiritual content or paid membership sites on social media. All of their online presence are free. The content of their online presence are made to align with their mission of equipping believers

Does the religious movement use other digital media?

ID:
9865

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 9866

- Blogs
- Websites
- YouTube

↳ Does the religious movement have their own description of the purpose of their use of other digital media?

ID:
9867

– No

Notes: There is no official description that indicates the purpose of their use of digital media

Does this religious movement use other methods to share its teachings?

ID: 9869

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 9870

- Dramatic performance

Does the religious movement use sponsorship of externally held events (e.g., of spiritual events, cultural festivals or sports teams)?

ID: 9871

– No

Notes: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis does not use sponsorship of externally held events such as spiritual events, cultural festival or sport team. Their documented activities focus on hosting their own internal events

Does this religious movement have strategies for interacting with outside media outlets?

ID: 9872

– No

Notes: There is no formalised strategy for interacting with the media outlets. Their outreach focuses on inward owned media like websites, social media, radio and events. Their platform such as YouTube Facebook are used to streamline their devotions, testimonies with no documented press release or interview with external news organization

Does this religious movement have strategies for interacting with academia?

ID:
9873

– No

Notes: There is no formalised strategy for interacting with the academia or partnering with universities. The group prioritize its own institutions like the annual school of ministry (ASOM), Living Jesus Ministerial Training College for biblical and ministerial equipping.

Is there anything important about media use and public relations that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 9877

– Specify: No

Notes: All the channel adopted for use in the Dream Centre of the Life oasis international church are Facebook, Instagram and Youtube

Organisational Structure

Leadership

Does the religious movement have a current leader or leaders? ID:

9880

– Yes

↳ Specify the name(s), date(s) of birth, country or countries of origin and primary language(s) of the leader or leaders ID: 9881

– Name(s): Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun

– Date(s) of birth: May 12, 1962

– Country or countries of origin: Nigeria

– Primary language(s) of the leader or leaders: Yoruba and English languages

Notes: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International church operates under a hierarchical order of a Pastor led organisation. It is currently under the leadership of the founder who is regarded as the senior Pastor commissioned directly by God in 1984. He is the President of the mission who oversees the leadership of the mission. His wife Rev (Mrs) Oyenike Areogun is the co-leader of the group

↳ What is the biological sex of the current leader or leaders? ID: 9882

– Male and female couple

Notes: The religious group is led by Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun and his wife Rev (Mrs) Oyenike

Areogun

- ↳ Is the relationship status of the current leader or leaders known? ID: 9883
– Yes
- ↳ Select all that apply: ID: 9884
– Monogamously Married
Notes: The leaders are married and in a monogamous family
- ↳ Do the current leaders have children? ID: 9885
– Yes
- ↳ Are the leader's children considered spiritually exceptional? ID: 9886
– Yes
Notes: The leaders are married with children.
- ↳ Do we know how the leadership is appointed? ID: 9887
– No
Notes: The specific ways of how leadership is appointed is not explicit spelt. Apart from the fact that the group has never change leader, there is no document or formal procedure in the direction
- ↳ Is the leadership advised by others? ID: 9889
– No
Notes: There is no indication of such existence. The group operate a founder led model where the founder who is the general overseer decides and appoint others who can work with him based on prophetic and his divine inspiration.
- ↳ Is leadership formally under a collective body (e.g., a council of elders, governing committee, or similar group)? ID: 9891
– No
Notes: The group does not have any known collective body or group of individuals who control

the organization. The kind of organization that exist in Dream centre of the life Oasis international church is Pastor centric in nature. The structure emphasize the church government under the leadership of the local Pastor. Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun as the founder and General Overseer while his wife Rev (Mrs) Oyenike Areogun as the vice president holding primary authority. The administrative functions provide operational support for the workings with the group. While the ultimate decision are made within the founding pastoral hierarchy

To what extent does the religious movement agree with the following statement: "Members or disciples are expected to accept the religious leader's pronouncements on all matters without question or dissent."? ID: 9897

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The statement members or disciples are expected to accept the religious leader's pronouncement on all matters without hesitation or dissenting opinion are largely agreed and emphasize in the group. This stems from the pastor-centric nature of the group

How many levels exist in the religious leadership hierarchy? ID: 9894

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 3

Notes: The Dream centre of the Life Oasis International Church operates 3 level of religious leadership. This religious leadership dictates who things work in the group. The leadership model is pastor centric in nature. This Pastor centric model emphasized the top, the supporting ministry and the functions and local operation. The first level is the founder /general overseer level. This level hold the highest authority. It is at the level where the general overseer, the president operate. It is the base where vision and agenda are set, oversee across all branches and where vital decisions are made.

How do people become leaders or reach senior positions in the organisation? ID: 9895

– Appointment by current leader

– Other:: There is no specific process to attain leadership position

Notes: In Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church, there is no specific process documented for attaining or reaching a senior position. However leadership advancement can be linked to a prophetic calling, ministry gifting and the founder recognition of e potential of such leader. More to this, is the participation in ASOM and LJMTTC . These are important as it serves as the training ground for the workers in the group and beyond.

What qualities or abilities does the religious movement value in current ID: 9898

leadership?

– Other:: Prophetic teaching and leadership skill

Notes: The group values prophetic calling and teaching ministry. Teaching ministry is held in high honour and ability to effectively administered and put things in shape are qualities that the current leader exemplifies.

Are organisational leadership roles formally appointed on a geographical or regional basis? ID: 9899

– No

Notes: The organisational leadership is determine by founder of the the who is the current General Overseer

Membership

Estimated number of members of the religious movement within designated geographical region: ID: 9900

If the estimated number of members is based on external counting (.e.g, census report or scholarly assessment), clearly state the source and provide a reference. If the estimate is based on internal reporting by the religious movement, clearly state the source and provide a reference.

– Specify: 40,000-70,000

Notes: The group does not have official population figure. It is therefore put between estimated to be within the range of 40000- 70000

When the religious movement reports internal demographic data, is it consistent with independent external assessments? ID: 9901

– No

Notes: The religious group does not engage or report any demographic data.

– No

Notes: The religious group does not engage or report any demographic data.

When does full membership begin? ID: 9902

– Baptism or purification rite

- Completing religious education or training
- Confirmation or profession of faith
- Demonstration of knowledge by passing tests
- Formal acceptance by leadership
- Participation in exclusive rituals or ceremonies
- Public declaration or testimony of belief
- Ordination or consecration

Notes: When a Pearson join the church, to be a full member you must attend believers class for 52 weeks study. After the completion of the study you will be considered as a bonafide member and a graduation will be done which signifies your full membership. However you can received membership before you complete your 52 weeks classes in as much you have have made up your mind to become member, and abide by the church protocol. To join the work force or become a steward, you must have completed the Believers class. There are specialized training like "Men in Ministry Mentorship Program" or "Women in Ministry Mentorship Program". There is also " Pastor in Training Program " of which determine your posting for assignment if you vied for leadership position.

Is the religious movement linked to a specific country or ethnic group?

ID: 9903

– No

Notes: The religious group is not affiliated to any specific group. The group was founded in Ilesa in Osun State by Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun in 1989. The founder Areogun is a Yoruba man but the religious group he founded was a multi ethnic outreach.. The church has no link to Yoruba nationalism .

Do members often live communally?

ID:

9908

– No

Notes: Members of the Life Oasis International Church do not live communally. The church operate like a typical Nigerian Pentecostal network. It has independent branches across some cities and town in Nigeria and in outside Nigeria. The church does not operate any shared housing or communal sort of lifestyles

What is the typical residential environment for members of this religious movement?

ID: 9911

- Urban
- Rural
- Mixed

Notes: The members of this religious group come from urban, suburban and standard family house across Nigeria. At Osogbo where the headquarters of the church is located, many of the members reside in middle to low income neighborhood. There are members of the church who live among the high income earner, middle and low income earner.

How would you best describe the stability of the religious movement membership? ID: 9912

- Expected to be lifelong, but members can leave
- Lifelong membership regardless of personal beliefs or choice

Is membership exclusive, meaning members cannot have other religious affiliations? ID: 9913

- Yes

Notes: Member in life oasis International Church cannot maintain any other religion affiliation. The church is exclusive. Every member is expected to maintain adherence to the teaching of the church and uphold all the practices as set in the teaching of all church. The members are to adhere strictly to the doctrine of the holy spirit , baptism, biblical inerrancy and leadership under Rev. Olusola Ayodele Areogun

Is there a probationary period before someone becomes a full member? ID: 9914

- No

Notes: There is no formal probationary period before one can become a full member. However new attendee cannot be given platform to serve as a worker until when he or she must have passed through the requisite training to becoming a worker. Members are allowed to grow organically through their involvement in church activities.

Is it possible for members to attend services and events organised by other religious movements? ID: 9915

- Yes

Notes: It is possible to attend services and event organised by other religious movement. However, such practices are not encouraged as many of the group members may frown at such and deem it as a lack of commitment to their church . Of course there is no official information regarding that yet it is a not a practice that is hidden

Does the religious movement allow non-members to attend services, take courses, or access teachings? ID: 9916

- Yes

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 9917

- Invited guest
- Member of the public
- Potential member

Notes: Non members are allowed to attend services and access teaching. However for specialized courses, it's only for members

Are members permitted to critically examine or challenge the religious movement's literature and directives? ID: 9918

– No

Notes: Members are taught obedience to the authority and the church. They are taught loyalty and firm believe in the scripture. It is therefore rare to have member of the religious challenging the literature or directive of the church.

What is the religious movement's approach to members engaging with literature from other religious movements? ID: 9919

– Strongly discouraged

Notes: Members are discouraged from engaging in literature from other religious movement. The bible and others christian literature books written by the founder are the literature recommended for the religious group

Does the religious movement set behavioural expectations for its members? ID: 9920

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 9921

- Child rearing commitments
- Commitments regarding interactions with other religions
- Dating and marriage commitments
- Financial commitments
- Other:: The church maintains a unique standard of holiness

Notes: Every member of the life Oasis International Church is expected to live holy life, submit to authority and pastoral leadership and requires obedience to the church teachings

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 9921

- Child rearing commitments
- Commitments regarding interactions with other religions
- Dating and marriage commitments
- Financial commitments
- Other:: The church maintains a unique standard of holiness

Notes: Every member of the life Oasis International Church is expected to live holy life, submit to authority and pastoral leadership and requires obedience to the church teachings

↳ Are there consequences for members who violate behavioural expectations? ID: 9922

– No

Notes: The church does not impose formal punishment like excommunication, or shunning of members violating behavioural expectations. However corrective measure such as teachings and pastoral counselling are in place to put back those who slide away in the right track

Does the religious movement maintain a tiered or differentiated membership structure? ID: 9924

– No

Notes: Life Oasis International Church does not maintain a tiered or differentiated membership structure. All committed members or attendees functions as equal brethren or church family

Does the religious movement identify key figures other than its leaders or founders who have been important to the self-understanding of members? ID: 9928

– No

Notes: The church does not identify any key leader or founder other than its founder and leader in person of Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun and his wife who serve as the senior Pastor of the church

Is there anything important about membership that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 9929

– Specify: There is nothing specific about the member which are yet to be addressed

Minors

Are there minors in the religious movement? ID: 9930

– Yes

↳ Are there children who were born into the religious movement? ID: 9931

– Yes

↳ How many generations of children are part of the religious movement? ID: 9932

– Three or more

Notes: Many generation are already born into the religious group

↳ Do children born into the movement receive full membership status or complete initiation from birth? ID: 9933

– Yes

Notes: The children born into the movement are regarded as member

↳ Are minors born within the religious movement considered spiritually exceptional? ID: 9934

– No

Notes: The minors born into the religious movement are not considered spiritually exceptional

↳ Within the religious movement, are minors thought to have a special role in this lifetime? ID: 9935

– No

Notes: The church does not teach that minor have special role beyond preparing them for personal Faith and service like adult. The church equip them for maturity and mentor them to

discover their God's given dream

↳ Within the religious movement, are minors thought to have a special role in the afterlife? ID: 9936

– No

Notes: There is no such teaching like minor having special role in after life

↳ At what age do minors typically become full members? ID: 9937

– Enter age:: There is no specific age

Notes: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church does not specify age to become full members. Right from the young age the children are integrated into the church through family integration.

Does the religious movement provide guidance to its members about raising minors? ID: 9938

– Yes

↳ Does the religious movement provide guidelines for educating minors? ID: 9939

– Yes

↳ What kinds of education are encouraged for minors? ID: 9940

- Curriculum centred on sacred texts or doctrines
- Education designed to minimise outside influence
- Education as preparation for movement membership or leadership
- Educational achievements needed to get into university
- Taught by qualified teachers
- University level or higher education

Notes: The education for the children emphasized parental discipleship

↳ Are parents encouraged to withdraw their children from 'mainstream' education? ID: 9941

– Yes

↳ What type of schooling is provided?

ID: 9942

– Religious movement run boarding or residential schools

Notes: The Ministry runs a Christian boarding school called Destiny International College. It is a secondary school founded by the leaders.. Rev (Mrs) Oyenike Areogun received the vision for a world class secondary school providing girls with biblical foundation and academic excellence. Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun expanded it in 2011 to include boys as Destiny international college in Osogbo Nigeria

↳ Are minors permitted to have friends outside of the religious movement?

ID: 9943

– Other:: They are permitted to have friends outside the religious movement.

↳ Who is responsible for disciplining and punishing minors?

ID: 9944

– Other:: The school management is responsible to disciplines any erring students according to the government policy.

Notes: School policy explicitly forbid senior student disciplining thee junior. If there is and infraction, they are to report to the appropriate quarter who then handle the matter . There is a house parent who handle any case within the school's ecosystem

↳ Are there spiritual or theological reasons given for disciplining or punishing minors?

ID:
9945

– Yes

Notes: Destiny International College provide spiritual and theological reasons for disciplining minors. The school Christian philosophy must be upheld by the students. They are taught discipline as part of essential to develop strong character to build moral standard that will deepen their walk with God

↳ What kinds of disciplining and punishing are commonly used on minors?

ID: 9946

– Other:: No specific punishment is recommended

Notes: As a Christian school, with an house parent residing with the student, all discipline are handle through biblical lens. There is no specific harsh punishments or disciplinary method for the minors

↳ Are there child-focused events like summer camps or youth groups?

ID:
9947

– Yes

Notes: The religious group does have child focused events for the young mind. There is a youth initiatives like " Yielding Young Achievers " Zion pillars" " Distinguish Daughter of Destiny " all of them are dedicated children programs within the religious group

Is having children considered desirable for members or affiliates of the religious movement? ID: 9948

– Yes

↳ Is the movement explicitly pro-natalist, encouraging childbearing to raise its birthrate? ID: 9949

– Yes

Notes: The Church the Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International encourage child bearing. The church adhere to Pentecostal theology of biblical multiplication mandate .However the church does not support bearing children that would be abandoned by the parent

Is there anything important about minors that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 9950

– Specify: There is nothing important that has not been covered

Growth Strategies

Does the religious movement accept new members or converts? ID: 9951

– Yes

↳ Are some members of the religious movement expected to engage in proselytising or missionary work? ID: 9952

– Yes

↳ Does the religious movement set targets for the number of new members that need to be recruited? ID: 9953

– No

Notes: The church has a mission outreach which involves reaching villages and planting church. It is done periodically but there is no set target for numbers of people to be recruited

↳ Does the religious movement reward or recognise members who are most successful in recruiting new members? ID: 9954

– No

Notes: The church does not reward those who are most successful in recruiting new members

↳ Do members receive either direct or indirect financial incentives for recruitment? ID: 9955

– No

Notes: Members do not received either direct or indirect incentives for recruitment

↳ Are there face-to-face recruitment strategies? ID: 9956

- Campus-based recruitment
- Charity or service events as outreach
- Missionary trips
- Personal witnessing
- Presence in public spaces, such as malls, markets, transportation hubs or festivals
- Recruitment through youth programming

Notes: The church encourages members to invite people to church in various format. It can be through one on one conversation or group evangelism.

↳ Are there traditional media recruitment strategies? ID: 9957

- Newspapers
- Radio programming
- Television programming

Notes: Life Oasis International Church actively engage in traditional media evangelism through radio and television. There is a daily radio program beingh hosted by Rev. Olusola Ayodele Areogun and Rev. (Mrs) Oyenike Areogun. It is called "Living by the Answer" the program runs a daily radio/TV program. It runs on local and international channels across Nigeria, Africa, UK, Europe and USA. The print media distribute daily free devotional guide.

↳ Are there Internet-based recruitment strategies? ID: 9958
–Other:: The church does not use any popular influencer
Notes: The church itself has a department that is engaged with online evangelism. They also have those who are responsible for the social media. They are in charge of the church online activities

↳ Does the religious movement target particular groups of people when seeking new members? ID: 9960
– No
Notes: The religious group target all group of people. It does. not matter where you come from

↳ Do new members describe having conversion experiences? ID: 9962
– Yes
Notes: The conversion experiences vary. It build faith and encouraged those who have challenge that its not over for them

↳ Are conversion experiences shared with others in the religious movement? ID: 9963
– Yes
Notes: Conversion experiences are share to build faith of others

↳ Are conversion experiences shared with potential new members? ID: 9964
– Yes

↳ Are conversion experiences characterised by: ID: 9965
– Dramatic personal transformations (e.g., restored health or new physical powers)
– Intellectual or cultural pursuits
– Personal or existential search
– Spiritual experiences

Do members or leaders use personal testimonies to recruit new members? ID: 9966
– Yes

↳ How are testimonials used within the religious movement?

ID:
9967

- Framed as evidence of supernatural intervention
- Published in books, pamphlets or the Internet
- Used as teaching materials for outreach training

Notes: Testimonies are used as evidence of supernatural intervention while fueling outreach programs through multiple media formats

Has the religious movement been accused of using deceptive or manipulative methods in recruitment?

ID: 9968

– No

Notes: The religious movement has never been accused of using deceptive or manipulative methods in their recruitment. The church does employ open invitationals through radio and TV broadcast. There has never been a reported case of deceptive method for recruitment

Is there anything important about growth strategies that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly.

ID:
9973

- Specify: The growth in the Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church can be linked to sound teaching, impactful prayer and other outreach programs

Movement boundaries

To what extent would this religious movement agree with the following statements: "Movement outsiders cannot be trusted."

ID:
9974

– +2 moderately endorsed

Notes: The church agrees to a moderate extent that movement outsiders cannot be trusted. In part of the doctrinal practices of the church, there is the part of strong church government under the local Pastor and exclusive Holy Spirit authority within its structure. The group views other groups as potentially deficient in Pentecostal fullness or vision alignment. It therefore fosters caution towards external influences.

To what extent would this religious movement agree with the following statements: "Movement outsiders are not fully human."

ID: 9975

– -3 strongly opposed

Notes: The church disagreed with such a statement that movement outsiders are not fully human. As part

of what the Church uphold all human are created in God's image. Through the first man, all men became sinners. God provided atonement through Christ's death and resurrection. Man must be redeemed and come to the saving knowledge of Christ . This aligned with the Pentecostal's theology.

Does the religious movement encourage members to view the movement as their family? ID: 9976

– Yes

↳ Does the movement use kinship terms to refer to one another? ID: 9977

– Yes

Notes: The movement encouraged members to view the movement as their family. Spiritual family is emphasised that portray members as one family in the body of Christ. Believers Bible Conferences build communal intimacy with Rev Olusola' Areogun's leadership. The dream centre is seen as a nurturing oasis for dream realization where members support one another like siblings in kingdom services

Does the religious movement have negative views toward out-groups? ID: 9978

– No

Notes: The religious group does not exhibit a known negative views towards other group.. The church does organise interdenominational program that teach pastors on effectiveness leadership and on other kingdom services

Does the religious movement endorse violence towards any out-groups? ID: 9981

– No

Notes: The group has never had any know case for endorsing or promoting violence. The church has rather continued in teaching people on how to discover their potential and fulfil their God's given vision

Does the religious movement engage in practices aimed at defending its members or the collective group? ID: 9982

– No

Notes: The group does not engage in practices specifically aimed at defending it's members or collective group beyond pastoral care. The group is. a compliant Nigerian Pentecostal church. The church makes use of ushers gated compound and event marshals. The teaching of the group believes in Holy Spirit covering and victory over darkness through faith in God.

Does the religious movement use spiritually symbolic weapons?

ID: 9994

– No

Notes: Life Oasis International Church does not use spiritually symbolic weapons . As a typical Nigerian Pentecostal group, it rather employed prayer, fasting and Holy Spirit baptism, speaking in tongue and binding and loosing in Jesus name.

Are individuals encouraged to establish personal defences related to cybersecurity and identity protection?

ID: 9996

– No

Notes: The group does not encourage members to establish personal defenses related to cyber security or identity protection. The group teaching centres on Holy Spirit empowerment, prayer against witchcraft and prosperity through faith in God. The message of the founder especially the broadcast like "Living by the Answer " and special events like "Web of Wisdom" proffer ways on how to live victoriously without references to personal defence or issues related to cyber security

Is there anything important about movement boundaries that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly.

ID:
9997

– Specify: No

Notes: The Life Oasis International Church focuses on spiritual defences which can be gotten through Holy Spirit. There is nothing special on movement boundaries that are not yet covered.

Leaving or Disaffiliating

Are there formal procedures for leaving the religious movement?

ID: 9998

– No

Notes: When people decide to leave there is no formal or special procedure. Membership appears informal, tied to the attendance, participation in service and are in alignment to the leadership than enrolment . People when leaving do not need a written notice, church approval or interview whenever they choose to leave they can leave. However looking from the lens of Pastoral authority and prophetic guidance and covering, when people leave they are likely to be said to have disengage from the fatherly covering. Some members may decide not to relate with the individual who leaves believing he has left spiritual covering.

Is it possible to be expelled from the religious movement?

ID: 10000

– No

Notes: In this religious group, there is no formal expulsion policy that is documented. Even the religious group doesn't have documented disciplinary procedure for removing members. Notwithstanding, there exists Pastor led authority to address various issues privately rather than through public glare. Under the current leadership, issues like doctrinal dissent, moral failure and any related matters would likely be handled through counselling, prophetic ministration of the pastor

Are former members treated differently depending on the circumstances of their departure (e.g., lapse, renunciation, or expulsion)? ID: 10001

– No

Notes: Officially there are no documented evidence that suggest that former members are treated differently but in practice it has been noted that former members who left the group do not receive warmth or kind fellowship when they show up in the gathering of the group. They are given the silent dose and sometimes people keep their distance from them

Primary sources produced by former members: ID: 10013

Sensitive documents might be held by Inform and accessible upon reasonable request

– If available, attach PDFs: It's unavailable

Notes: There are no official or respondent with a concrete evidence on expulsion or renunciation who had it documented

Are former members able to join events or activities as non-members? ID: 10002

– Yes

Notes: Former members or any non members are privilege to join events and activities . The church operate open access policy that allows both members and non members to have access and participate in their program.

Are former members permitted to maintain social contact with friends and family who remain in the religious movement? ID: 10003

– Yes

Notes: Former members are free and permitted to maintain social contact with friends and family. There is no direct instruction or documents that forbid such. In principle members are free to relate with their friends and family but in practical , the essential family and social fire tends to be on the lowest ebbs as relating with people especially those who leave the group in most cases are usually not cordial. The non members who are just program members are usually not affected

Are former members regarded as being outside the movement's sphere of spiritual protection? ID:10004

– No

Notes: Officially the teaching and doctrine of the group does not capture the former attendees of the group. The doctrinal focus on protection is based on the obedience to God, faith in God and not mainly on church membership. However, there are cases when those who were members and left the group were told that they are now without covering.

Are former members considered evil or dangerous? ID: 10005

– No

Notes: Former members are not really considered as dangerous or evil, yet they are practically not embraced with open arms. A member who leaves is considered to be opened to attack of the world

Do former members report encountering significant barriers when attempting to leave the religious movement? ID:10006

– No

Notes: There has been no formal or pronounced report of any form of barrier encountered when attempting to leave. To leave a member can decide when and how. However pressure may be mounted to know why the person wants to leave. Individual in the category can also be counseled against such an idea. Aside from the pastoral effort and pressure to drop such idea, no serious effort can be pointed as a serious barrier

Is there anything important about leaving or disaffiliating that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID:10014

– Specify: No

Notes: There is nothing important about leaving or disaffiliating that has not been treated

Is there anything important about the organisational structure that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 9878

– Specify: No

Notes: The organisation structure of the group has been covered. It involves three level of hierarchy which are the first founder/ General overseer where vision are set and oversee. This is followed with the senior pastors and five fold ministries . This office is occupied by Rev (Mrs) Oyenike Areogun who is the senior pastor of the dream centre and the vice president of the ministry. The third level is the pastors and five fold ministries. The local pastors leads branches which are scattered in Nigeria, UK and in USA

Describe or upload relevant documents pertaining to organisational structure:

ID:
9879

– Specify: Description of the organization structure

Notes: The leadership of the church can be described in this format. At the top hierarchy of the church is the founder and General Overseer of the church with his wife who serves as the senior Pastor and vice President of Sola Areogun Ministries. This is the apex of leadership that provide vision and oversight function for the church The second leadership cadre is the branch governance. This places authority under local Pastor who are branch Pastor across various location where the branches are located like Oyo, Ondo, Lagos, Kwara, Abuja, UK and US The other hierarchy is the ministry Arms. This is a specialized unit that include Bible school, Abundant Life House which is a publishing arm, and the media

Beliefs and Worldview

General Worldview

Is orthodoxy emphasised?

ID: 10016

– Yes

Notes: The Dream centre emphasised Christian orthodoxy in its doctrine . The group belief aligned with divine inspiration of the scripture. The group consider the bible as infallible words of God. It also believes in the Trinity that the God heads and the person therein are co -equal and co- eternal. Also the group believe in the virgin birth, sinless life, atoning death , resurrection, ascension and the second coming, the millennia reign, justification, sanctification, baptism by immersion and Holy Communion.

Does the religious movement believe in a fundamental unifying principle underlying all spirituality (“concordances”)?

ID:
10017

– No

Notes: The group does not believe in fundamental unifying principle underlying all spirituality. Their doctrine present Jesus Christ and biblical revelation as the exclusive path to truth. It does not accommodate any form of universalism framework or incorporates non Christian teaching

Does the religious movement teach that all religions are expressions of one underlying truth?

ID: 10018

– No

Notes: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church does not teach anything that portrays that all religion are expressions of an underlying truth. The group doctrinal statements affirm that salvation come through the atoning death and resurrection of Christ. It also uphold personal faith in Christ with no accommodation for any other faith . The group emphasised Jesus virgin birth , sinless life,

millennial reign and bible as the sole authority for the believers

Does the religious movement teach that all mystical experiences point to the same ultimate reality? ID: 10019

– No

Notes: The religious group does not teach that all mystical experiences point to the same ultimate reality. It rather teach exclusivity that all the mystical experiences like dream, vision, prophetic ministrations and others are direct communication from e Holy Spirit. There is rejection of syncretism in the teaching of The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church. The ultimate reality of the religious group centres on the atoning death and resurrection of Jesus and his millennia reign

Does the religious movement teach that their knowledge represents an “inner teaching” of all religions? ID: 10020

– No

Notes: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church does not teach that the movement represent the inner teaching of all religion. The official beliefs of the group is exclusively christocentric doctrine , the virgin birth, the Trinity, atoning death and resurrection of Jesus Christ.

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: ID: 10021
"The universe is a good place."

– -2 Moderately opposed

Notes: This assertion that the universe is a good place will not be fully agreed . This is because the doctrine of the Dream Centre of the Life Oasis Church recognises God's original plan for his creation to be good but when man fall, he brought corruption and death upon himself . Therefore everything needs redemption which can only be gotten through Christ. The teaching of the group addresses fallen world theology. Man is believed to have fallen and needed redemption. The sin of man in disobedience to God brought a grave consequence and there is a need for human redemption

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: ID: 10022
"The universe is structured to function effectively and in accordance with its inherent order."

– -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: This is because after the fall of man, the universe requires atonement. The only way to do that is through Christ atonement therefore the statement that universe is structure to function effectively and in accordance with inherent order cannot hold sway. The universe needs redemption

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement:
"The universe is seen as existing for an ultimate or greater purpose."

ID: 10023

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The universe exists for the ultimate greater goal. The doctrine of divine teleology affirms that God is the creator of the universe. He does not create in vain he has a purpose for this creation. The teaching of the founder align with this that God is the creator of universe. Human existence has a divine purpose and all things are for the glory of God which is the ultimate plan.

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement:
"The universe is regarded as a genuine and objective reality, not as an illusion."

ID: 10024

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The group strongly endorsed the statement that the universe is regarded as genuine and objective reality and not as an illusion. The teaching of the group strongly affirm God as the creator and sustainer of a real physical universe. This is evidence in Christ incarnation. Christ is considered as fully God and became man fully

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement:
"The universe is seen as operating on principles that are orderly, consistent and coherent."

ID: 10025

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The doctrine of divine order is believe to affirm this statement that "the universe is seen as operating on principles that are orderly and consistent". God created all things but satanic intrusion brought disruption of which Christ will restore during millennial reign

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement:
"It is believed that genuine randomness and unpredictability exist within the universe."

ID: 10026

— -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The teaching of the group is opposed to the statement that genuine randomness and unpredictability exist in the universe. The teaching uphold that through obedience to God spirituality warfare can be won when in alignment with God's words. Believers are to key into prophetic words to live victoriously

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement:
"The world is seen as beautiful."

ID: 10027

— +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The church affirms this teaching that the universe exists for the ultimate greater purpose. Through

the teaching of the founder and the vision of the which is helping men to realize their God given dream, the statement the world is seen as beautiful is strongly endorsed

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: ID:10028
"The world is seen as interesting and exciting."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The world is seen as interesting and exciting when life and purpose is discovered. Part of the teaching of the church is based on understanding and fulfilling Gods given vision. The teaching of the founder portray circumstances as meaningful test where believers discern Gods will , and is able to overcome challenges through divine Strategies . Through this life is interesting and exciting

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: ID:10029
"The world is understood as hierarchical, with elements ranked according to their relative importance."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The statement that the world is understood as hierarchical with elements ranked according to their relative importance is strongly endorsed. There is practical ranking and order in the things of God. The ministry teaches order, divine will over human circumstances.

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: ID:10030
"The world is regarded as a realm in which nearly everything holds significance."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The statement that the world is regarded as a realm in which everything hold significance is strongly endorsed. The teaching of Rev Areogun uphold that everything is working and serving divine purpose. Therefore God's creation is inherently meaningful with everything working for the ultimate goal

How would the religious movement be characterised according to Roy Wallis' 1984 ID:10031
typology of new religious movements?

World-rejecting movements view the wider society as corrupt, impure, or spiritually misguided and seek to withdraw or reject mainstream values. World-Affirming Movements embrace the world and aim to help people flourish within it, often through self-development, personal empowerment or spiritual enhancement. World-Accommodating Movements neither reject nor affirm the world, but instead seek spiritual renewal within existing traditions. They often aim to deepen faith or enhance spirituality without challenging broader social norms.

– World-accommodating

Notes: Considering The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church in Wallis's typology, it will be

characterized as world accommodating. This is because the church accepts mainstream churches while focusing on enriching members spiritual lives. The church does request obedience to the Lord and a level of commitment to the group yet it does not request complete withdrawal from worldly occupation or lifestyle.

Do the religious movement's teachings present the world in dualistic terms, such as good versus evil or spiritual versus material? ID:10032

– Yes

↳ Are there clear distinctions between good and evil? ID:10033

– Yes

Notes: There are distinction between good and evil. Everything good comes from God and evil from the devil. Good is doing the right thing in the light of the scripture and according to God's will while evil is rejecting God's invitation and walking in a self-willed against God

↳ Are there supernatural beings that are believed to embody or represent this dualism? ID:10034

– Yes

Notes: There are supernatural who are believed to represent these dualism. Primarily we have God and the angel. Also satan and demon, witches and wizard, familiar spirit and the likes

↳ Does the religious movement teach a division between flesh and spirit? ID:10035

– Yes

Notes: The teaching of the founder clearly separate the division that exist between the flesh and the spirit. Their teaching is consistent with Pentecostal theology. The teaching portray the flesh as weak and resistant to the spirit. A renewed mind however is the one that received divine guidance from the Holy Spirit. Flesh must be subdue through obedience to God's words

↳ Is dualism viewed as complementary energies like yin/yang or Shakti/Shiva? ID:10036

– No

Notes: The teaching of the group does not view dualism as complementary energy like yin/yang, or shakti /Shiva. The teaching of the church emphasised Christ ultimate victory and the believers' authority over evil through the Holy Spirit

Does this religious movement consider the natural world to be sacred?

ID:10037

– No

Notes: The teaching of the Dream centre does not consider the natural world to be sacred . Though it considered the world as the creation of God. The world need redemption and this can only be gotten through Christ. The world is marred with sins and the only way is through the atoning death of Christ that can make the world to be sacred. The world is profane

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement? ID:10038
"All entities are regarded as possessing consciousness, including animals, plants, rocks, rivers and planets."

– -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The Assertion would be strongly opposed that "all entities are regarded as possessing consciousness including animals, plants, rocks,rivers and planets". The church only affirms consciousness only for human. Other inanimate nature are serving divine purposes but they lack personal awareness. Only human created in the image of God possesses human-spirit consciousness

Does the religious movement believe that the universe is imbued with a complex, plural, hierarchical life force ("living nature")?

ID: 10039

– No

Notes: Life Oasis International Church teaches that God is the creator and maker of the universe. Everything is under his singular sovereignty with human who are made in the image of God to exercise dominion over nature. Elements like animals, plants, rivers and other things in physical realm are to serve divine purpose. Therefore the religious group does not believe that the universe is imbued with a complex, plural hierarchical life force

Do members believe that natural disasters reflect the emotional states or disturbances of nature spirits?

ID:
10043

– No

Notes: There is no such teaching that natural disasters reflect the emotional states or disturbances of the nature of spirits. In the Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church teaching attribute disaster and hardship to the workings of demon, principalities, witchcraft or satanic opposition rather than diffuse spiritual emotion.

Are animals believed to possess higher spiritual awareness than commonly recognised?

ID:
10044

– No

Notes: Animals are not believed to possess higher spiritual awareness than commonly recognized. Animals are under human and are never considered as having any spiritual inclination. Human alone who bear the image of God with spirit consciousness for relationship with God are considered to have the life of God and spiritual awareness

Are some places viewed as spiritually stronger or more “alive” than others?

ID:

10046

– No

Notes: No place is viewed or considered spiritually stronger or more alive than others. Of course the teaching of the Life Oasis recognises that some places are under demonic influence. These places are occupied rather than inherently evil. Spiritual authority reside in believer and Holy Spirit anointing is upon the church. However through the gathering of believers and obedience to God, the presence of God will manifest heavily

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: "Everything is believed to be connected to everything else."

ID:

10048

– -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The church is strongly opposed to the statement that " everything is believed to be connected to everything else" The teaching of the founder emphasise the believers separation from the worldly system through Holy Spirit empowerment and obedience to God's words. The creator of the universe is sovereign. Human being bears his image and he rules over all. The church does not teach any universal interconnectedness or holistic unity across entities that exist.

Does the religious movement believe in real and symbolic correspondences between all things in the universe (“correspondences”)?

ID:

10049

– No

Notes: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church does not believe in real symbolic correspondences between all things and the universe. The teaching in the church employ biblical symbolism like dream prophetically interpreted for spiritual guidance

Does the religious movement promote a belief in or aspiration toward returning to a “pure” or original natural state?

ID: 10056

– No

Notes: The church does not promote a belief or aspirations toward returning to a pure original natural state. The teachings of the church emphasized victory over sin, sickness and poverty through the finished work of Christ

Does the religious movement express concern for maintaining the health of the environment? ID: 10057

– No

Notes: The church does not express concern about the health of the environment. The teaching of the church focuses on Holy Spirit empowerment, faith based prosperity healing and deliverance. The Church does not lay claim to any green initiative or any environmental program. The church rather focus on the agenda of making men realise their God given agenda

Does the religious movement have a position on climate change? ID: 10059

– No

Notes: The church does not have any position on climate change. The church is particular on how to make people realise their God's given dream through explicit teaching of the bible and other program of the church

Is the religious movement actively involved in environmental activism, such as protests, direct action or land conservation efforts? ID: 10061

– No

Notes: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church has never been involved in environmental activism or any kind of protest either in direct action or on any land conservation effort. The church focuses on building bridge between God and man so that human can be reconciled back to God.

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10062
"People are seen as superior to the natural environment."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The church would strongly endorsed the statement that "people are seen as superior to the natural environment" this is because the teaching of the founder emphasise biblical dominion which draws its messages from Genesis 1:28. The concept affirms that God has given human dominion over all of His creation. Human bears God's image he is therefore elevated to rule over God's other creature

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10063
"People are seen as part of the natural environment."

– -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The statement that people are seen as part of the natural environment would strongly be opposed by this religious group this is because human are created in the image of God and have received mandate dominion over all other creature. The sermon of Rev Olusola Areogun has severally stressed

victory over earthly challenges through faith. Man has the mandate to dominate the earth and subdue it for divine purposes

Humans

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10064
"People are considered inherently good and just."

– -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The statement that says "people are considered inherently good and just" can not be endorsed by this religious group. Life Oasis International Church affirms humanity's fall through Adam. The sinful nature is stressed in the belief of the group. The sin of Adam rendered all human to become sinner . Therefore man need to be reconciled with God. The faith in Christ atoning death and acceptance of this gift by man brings restoration and reconciliation between man and God .

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10065
"People are believed to get what they deserve."

– -2 Moderately opposed

Notes: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis international Church would disagreed to a certain level with the statement that says " people get what they deserve " This is because the statement is much of a karma like saying. However in the theology of Pentecostal that the group uphold, grace is emphasised and can render forgiveness, salvation , mercy and many more. Christ is presented as one who forgives and grant mercy even to the undeserved

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10066
"Moral truth is viewed as absolute, not relative."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The church agreed that " Moral truth is viewed as absolute and not relative" this is because the group hold the bible as the infallible words of God. The group believes that God's words is unchanging, the standard for the right and wrong remain the same. The church also teaches that humanity's fallen nature requires regeneration. No man can claim to be holy and righteous without accepting the atoning death and resurrection of Christ . It is only through faith in Christ that man can be saved. This is absolute to the group

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10067
"People are seen as having more rights than responsibilities."

– -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The idea that people are seen as having more right than responsibilities may not go well within this group. This is because the theology of work or obligations are entrenched in their teachings. The teaching stresses believers duties like giving, holy living, ministry service, discipline and many other responsibilities as attached to their calling. Their faithfulness to their service will grant them more opportunities and promotion before God and man

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10068
"The universe is believed to need people for something important. "

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: Life Oasis International Church would strongly agreed that the universe need people for something important. This is because the purpose of God for the creation of universe is for it to be inhabited. It is therefore part of God's plan to make the universe habitable therefore he created man in his image to exercise dominion on all of his creature . The founder of the church teaches on believer's role in subduing chaos in the world and living a life that affirms God's dominion mandate

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10069
"Life is seen as offering more pleasure than pain."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The church would agree strongly that life offer more pleasure than pain. This is because there is prosperity orientation of which cut across both spiritual and material blessings. The teaching of victory of sin, sicknesses and poverty through faith are well entrenched in the group. The founder's teaching promote all round prosperity and breakthrough from all circle of life.

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:
"Gratitude is central to teaching and practice." 10070

N/A for translation

– +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: This statement that "gratitude is central to teaching and practice " will be moderately endorsed. To a large extent, praise and thanksgiving are regarded as entry point to worship session that can provoke miracle. Teaching like gratitude, seed faith, giving and victory mindset are some of the views that are taught in the group. However before any kind of gratitude can be accepted, it must have come from a sanctified heart.

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:
"Forgiveness is central to teaching and practice." 10071

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The church would strongly agreed that forgiveness is central to teaching and practice. The core message of Christianity is salvation. Salvation brings along forgiveness. This is believed to be the doctrine of Christ. The teaching of the founder maintains that forgiveness is one of the fruit of spirit that members must possess

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10072
"Guilt and shame are seen as key elements in living a good life."

– -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The church would largely disagreed that guilt and shame are seen as key element in living a good life. The group subscribed to Pentecostal theology. The theology preaches freedom from sin's power through the atoning death of Christ. It also emphasise the baptism of the Holy spirit and deliverance from guilt through confession in Christ

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10073
"It is important to not cause harm to other humans."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: Life Oasis International Church would strongly agree that it is important to not cause harm to other human. The biblical Command of love your neighbour as yourself is classified as still very effective in the group

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10074
"It is important to not cause harm to other living beings beyond humans."

– +1 Mildly endorsed

Notes: Life Oasis would partially agree but not strongly emphasized avoiding harm to non-human living beings as central doctrine. Human are Gods steward on earth and are responsible for all other creature.. Human are to manage maintain and protect all other creature like animal etc. Animal welfare are secondary while humanm are primary

Supernatural Beings

Do members believe in beings viewed as supernatural?

ID:
10075

– Yes

↳ Are all deities viewed as aspects of one universal divine being ("monism")?

ID:10076

– No

Notes: The core supernatural entity believed by the group is God. They believed in the Trinity of the persons in the Godhead. God the father, Son and the Holy Spirit

↳ Is there one God or Goddess that is considered a “supreme being”?

ID:
10077

– Yes

Notes: God is believed to be the supreme being. He is incarnated in Christ Jesus and through faith in him humanity can be saved. The group does not believe in any Goddess

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10078
"God or the divine is believed to actively intervene in the lives of individuals."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The religious group would strongly agreed that God or divine is believed to actively intervene in the lives of individuals because God responds to faith in him, he answers prayer and handsomely reward obedience. There are messages from the founder which point to the direction

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10079
"God or the divine is believed to possess knowledge of how events and the course of evolution will unfold."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: Life Oasis International Church as a religious group believes in sovereign creator who has infinite knowledge. He is also a being who declare the end from the beginning. Therefore the group would strongly agreed that God possesses knowledge of how event and the course of evolution will unfold

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10080
"God or the divine is viewed as benevolent, not punitive."

– +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: God is considered as a God of mercy and not an angry God. He cares for His creation and does not want any to be destroyed.. The group affirms Gods loving kindness and benevolence. Through acceptance of the atoning death and faith in the resurrected Jesus one can attract mercy. However rejecting the free offer would lead to damnation.

Does the religious movement believe in multiple kinds of supernatural beings?

ID: 10081

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 10082

- Angels
- Deamons
- Spirits

Notes: The church believes in God as the head of all principalities and power. It also acknowledges the existence of angels, ministering spirit, Satan, and demon, which are adversaries

↳ Do God, the divine, or other supernatural beings intentionally interact with the material world? ID: 10083

- Yes

↳ Do they interact in dreams? ID: 10084

- Yes

Notes: God, the supernatural being do intentionally interact with material world

↳ Do they interact through trance possession? ID: 10085

- Yes

Notes: They use different medium to interact one of them is through trance

↳ Do they interact in waking, everyday life? ID: 10086

N/A for translation

- Yes

Notes: They interact with everyday life. Demon will want to show that it exist etc

↳ Do they interact through religious specialists? ID: 10087

- Yes

Notes: They can interact through religious specialist

↳ Do they interact through divination practices? ID: 10088

- Yes

Notes: They can interact through divination

↳ Do they interact through other means?

ID: 10089

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural can interact in many form

Does the movement believe in spiritual warfare or battling evil forces?

ID: 10090

– Yes

↳ Are evil forces or their effects frequently associated with the following factors? ID: 10091

– Antisocial behaviour

– Addiction

– Bed wetting

– Birth defects

– Criminal Behaviour

– Deamons/Jinn

– Developmental delays

– Ill health

– Financial misfortune

– Mental illness

– Generalised misfortune

– Natural disaster

– Poverty

Notes: The church believes that there is an ongoing conflict between good and evil and Satan is the father of all lies and evil. He is the originator of all ill-luck and affliction that are troubling human

Can supernatural beings temporarily inhabit or influence a person?

ID: 10092

– Yes

↳ Can supernatural possession occur without a person's consent? ID: 10093

ID: 10093

– Yes

Notes: The teaching of the church acknowledges the existence of demonic spirit. These demon can possess anyone who does not have Christ

↳ Can supernatural possession be seen as beneficial within the movement's teachings? ID: 10094

– No

Notes: Anyone who is possessed needs deliverance. Demonic possession is considered as evil

↳ Can supernatural possession be seen as harmful within the religious movement's teachings? ID: 10101

– Yes

↳ In what contexts do harmful possession appear? ID: 10102

– Bad luck

– Evil eye

– Ill mental health

– Ill physical health

– Life crises

– Sexual deviancy

Notes: Anyone who is possessed needs deliverance.

↳ Does the religious movement attempt to remove spirits believed to be possessing humans? ID: 10103

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 10104

– Other:: fastong and prayer Rough

↳ Is temporary spirit possession connected to social status within the movement? ID: 10105

– No

Notes: There is no such teaching of temporary spirit possession connected to social status in the church. The teaching of the church affirms Holy Spirit baptism with tongues as available to all believers regardless of hierarchy.

↳ Are beliefs in supernatural cohabitation with humans understood to coexist with material explanations, such as mental or physical health conditions? ID: 10110

– No

Notes: The Church does attribute any kind of disturbances like oppression, sickness, erratic behaviour, witchcraft or curses to demonic forces. However the teaching of the church emphasised victory over witchcraft and all works of darkness through faith in Jesus Christ.

↳ Are false or unauthorised spirit-possession claims punished within the religious movement? ID: 10111

– No

Notes: In this religious group, there is no room for claiming of spiritual possession as the church practices relies on pastoral oversight and communal discernment during service or deliverance sessions. Anything like spirit manifestation are usually addressed through teaching, prayer and formal correction than penalties.

Does the movement believe physical immortality can be achieved? ID: 10112

– No

Notes: There is no such thing as physical Immortality in the teaching and practices of the church. The group believes in the bodily resurrection at the return of Jesus Christ. The Pentecostal eschatological teachings are upheld that the saved will have eternal life and the lost will be damned

Does the religious movement teach belief in life after death? ID: 10114

– Yes

↳ Does the religious movement believe in reincarnation? ID: 10115

– No

Notes: The religious group believes in life after death for those who are saved. Christ is seen as the resurrection and life and he has the power to give life after death. For anyone to have assurance of life after death, he must believed in the resurrected Jesus and accept his Lordship

↳ Does the movement believe it is possible to achieve immortality by virtualising the self, such as through digitally uploading the mind? ID: 10119

– No

Notes: The group does not believe in attainment of immortality through virtualising self or through any digital means. To become immortal, believe in Jesus is the only way.

Are ancestors or the deceased considered important in the religious movement? ID: 10120

– No

Notes: Ancestors or the deceased are not considered as important in the religious movement. The dead are in Christ are seen as those resting in the lord and they will resurrect in the last day

Is salvation emphasised in this lifetime? ID: 10126

– Yes

Notes: Salvation is emphasised in this lifetime for anyone who wants to have eternal life. Part of the core message of the church is the doctrine of bodily return of Jesus Christ. The church teaches that Christ will come to take those who are saved during rapture of the church while the unsaved will have their domain in hell

Is there belief in an afterlife? ID: 10127

– Yes

↳ What happens to the physical body in an afterlife? ID: 10128

– Other:: Physical body will die off and celestial body will be given to the saved

Notes: The church believes that the earthly body cannot inherit incorruption because the earthly body is corruptible. The physical body will be changed to incorruptible one

Calendar and Time

Does the religious movement use the same calendar system as the dominant one in its country? ID: 10129

– Yes

Notes: Life Oasis International Church uses the same Gregorian calendar as the dominant system in Nigeria. The church uses familiar dates in all of its events.

Does the religious movement use an alternate calendar to the dominant one in its country? ID: 10130

– No

Notes: The religious group does not use alternate calendar to the dominant one in Nigeria. The group integrate Gregorian date into prophetic themes.

How does the religious movement conceptualise time? ID: 10132

– Predominately linear

Notes: The church conceptualized time predominantly as linear with a fixed starting point and separated into linear district. This goes in line with Pentecostals ways of viewing time from creation through Christ incarnation, death , and resurrection towards his return. Their calendar follows progressively with Pentecostals theology

Does the religious movement mark significant dates? ID:

– Specify: The church does mark the founding anniversaries , annual events and prophetic markers day 10133

Notes: Life Oasis International Church does mark her founding anniversaries to commemorate how it started in 1989 in ilesa. In the year 1984, Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun was commissioned into the ministry. Aside the above, there is annual crossover night that usually occurs in December 31. There are other annual event like Believers Bible conferences, August Missionary Outreach. Program (AMOP) that are regular in the church annual event

Does the movement teach a creation or origin story? ID:

– Yes 10134

↳ Is the origin of the world closely connected to the origin of the religious movement itself? ID: 10135

– No

Notes: The origin of the world is not closely connected to the origin of Life Oasis International Church. The church, the Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church can be traced to it's founder Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun in 1984 when he heeded the heavenly commission he had. That was the f genesis of what later became a church. In the year 1989, Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun launched a church in Ilesa, Nigeria. He claimed to have received mandate to make men realised their God's given vision

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10137
"Every event throughout eternity is thought to be predetermined."

– -2 Moderately opposed

Notes: The church would be opposed to the statement that every event throughout eternity is thought to be predetermined because in the teaching of the church, there is a conditional election based on foreseen faith, and atonement offer for anyone who chooses to accept and obey the Lord. There is room for repentance which can change the outcome of whether or not a man will be saved . There is no doubt anyway that the church affirms God's foreknowledge and his overarching plan yet there is room for salvation for all who chose to embrace. Christ while still alive

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:
"Events are seen as guided by a higher purpose." 10138

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The Church would surely agreed with the statement that events are seen as guided by the higher purpose. The church origin itself stems from Rev Olusola Areogun's divine commissioning. He received the mandate to demonstrate that Jesus is alive. He was given an assignment through divine encounter that he should help people to realised the God's given dream. This invariably show that the church believes in being guided by a higher purpose

World Transformations and Eschatology

Does the religious movement emphasise a coming transformation of the world? ID:
– Yes 10139

↳ Have transformational events been anticipated in the past? ID: 10140

– Yes

Notes: The time when it will happen is unknown

↳ Are specific date or dates given for the transformational event? ID: 10141

– No

Notes: No one knows the time

↳ Will the expected transformative event be sudden? ID: 10153

– Yes

Notes: The transformation of the world being expected would happen at the return of Christ. A earthly millennia reign of Christ will be established

↳ Does the religious movement claim the transformative event will restore certain people's rights to their land and governance? ID: 10154

– No

Notes: There is no such claim of restoration of land for some people. The eschatological reign on Christ affix Jerusalem as the capital where Christ will rule globally

↳ Will specific events precede the transformative event? ID: 10155

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 10156

- Advancement of science and knowledge
- Climate change
- Disease
- Displacement of the religious population
- Ethnic cleansing of a place
- Mass spiritual awakening
- Military defeat
- Military success
- Miracles
- Natural disasters
- Religious or spiritual revival
- Scoffing or ridicule
- War

Notes: There will be years of tribulations that will precede transformation of

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 10156

- Advancement of science and knowledge
- Climate change
- Disease
- Displacement of the religious population
- Ethnic cleansing of a place
- Mass spiritual awakening
- Military defeat
- Military success
- Miracles
- Natural disasters
- Religious or spiritual revival
- Scoffing or ridicule
- War

Notes: There will be years of tribulations that will precede transformation of earth

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 10156

- Advancement of science and knowledge
- Climate change
- Disease
- Displacement of the religious population
- Ethnic cleansing of a place
- Mass spiritual awakening
- Military defeat
- Military success
- Miracles
- Natural disasters

- Religious or spiritual revival
- Scoffing or ridicule
- War

Notes: There will be years of tribulations that will precede transformation of earth

↳ Is the transformative event tied to a specific location? ID: 10157

– No

Notes: The transformative event is the millennial reign of Christ on earth. It is not restricted to a specific early location. The Christ return will establish a worldwide 1000year rule on earth

↳ Should the transformative event be accelerated, if possible? ID: 10160

– No

Notes: It is fixed in the timeline of God to follow a divine sequential order. There will be rapture, tribulation Armageddon and then Christ returns. These are well believed as the prophetic timeline

↳ Do members of the religious movement need to perform specific tasks to bring about the transformative event? ID: 10161

– No

Notes: There is nothing that the member need to do or task to perform to bring the event of transformation to play. It has been designed as the return of Christ and no one knows the exact time of his fulfilment

↳ Must the leader or founder perform certain tasks to initiate the transformative event? ID: 10162

– No

Notes: The leader of the Life Oasis International Church cannot do anything about it. He has no task to perform to initiate the impending event

↳ Will non-members bring about the transformative event through their actions? ID: 10163

– No

Notes: Non members cannot bring about the transformative event through their action or

inaction. It is a divine timeline

- ↳ Is it possible to prevent the transformative event? ID: 10164
- No
- Notes: It is not possible to prevent it. The event is already decided and it would come to pass. The group strongly believe that there is hope for all who believe in Christ

- ↳ Is the transformative event expected to result from divine or spiritual intervention? ID: 10168
- Yes

- ↳ Is the transformative event understood as divine judgement? ID: 10169
- Yes
- Notes: It is a judgement of the inhabitant of the earth. The judgement comes before transformation of the earth

- ↳ What shape will the transformative event take? ID: 10170
- An agrarian paradise, or a return to the pre-fall state
- Conflict-free human order
- Ethnic harmony
- Eternal youth
- Living in harmony with nature
- No language barriers in communication
- Perfection of human capacities
- Perfect health
- Resurrection of dead
- Notes: It is a government under Christ, the earth will be purged of filth and there will be perfect order in the kingdom.

- ↳ Will anyone survive the transformative event? ID: 10171
- Yes

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 10172

– Other:: Everyone who had crossed over and survive the initial tribulations before the transformation will surely survive thereafter

↳ Will individuals have to be in a certain location to survive the transformative event? ID: 10173

– Yes

↳ Is there a known location that is considered safe? ID: 10174

– Enter in the text box:: a safe place for the transformative event is to be with the messiah

↳ Are only on-site members protected? ID: 10175

– No

Notes: all those who are on his side will surely be safe. By the time when messiah shall come all those who are wicked will be judge before the transformed earth

↳ Will members take part in violence or warfare as part of the transformative event? ID: 10176

– No

Notes: Members will have nothing to do either for taking part in violence or any kind of agenda to enforce the transformative event. The transformative event is a divine agenda and will be executed through the divine order

↳ Is a prophetic or messianic person expected to initiate the transformative event? ID: 10183

– Yes

↳ Is this prophetic or messianic person's whereabouts, or time of their coming, known? ID: 10184

– Coming in an unspecified time in distant future

Notes: The Messiah who will initiate the kingdom is Jesus Christ

↳ Is there a known purpose for the prophetic or messianic person? ID: 10185

– Other:: To set up the reign of God on earth

Notes: The purpose of the messianic person is centre on redemption, reign and eternal victory over evil. The Messiah is believe to be of virgin birth, sinless and has died atoning death and also resurrected from e dead. He will come again to set up his kingdom in the millennial reign

Is there anything important about beliefs and worldview that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 10015

– Specify: The church hold a distinctive position in helping people realized their God's given vision

Notes: The founder's mandate was distinct as he claimed to have been given supernatural empowerment in helping men to realized their dream and live a practical Christian life

Practices

Communal Ritual Practices

Does the religious movement organise group rituals? ID: 10187

– Yes

↳ What kinds of rituals? ID: 10188

– Communion services

– Faith healing

– Prophecy

– Spiritual counselling

– Thanksgiving services

– Worship and devotion

Notes: The church organise corporate worship, Sunday service, annual thanksgiving and several specialized gathering.

↳ During group rituals, do participants likely experience a sense of communitas or collective effervescence (i.e., a spontaneous, egalitarian bond that arises among individuals sharing a liminal experience)? ID: 10189

– Yes

Notes: During the services people are likely to experience *communitas* or collective effervescence. The gathering usually features extended praise, spontaneous tongues and prophetic utterances. During many of the conferences, all night prayer, crossover event, bonding are amplified.

↳ How frequently are members expected to attend group rituals?

ID: 10190

– Two to three times a week

Notes: In the Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church, the meetings time are on Sunday, Tuesday and Wednesday. However, there are stewards All Night meetings for various group which are held almost everyday of the week

↳ Are ritual roles assigned by gender?

ID: 10191

– No

Notes: There is no ritual role in the Dream centre of the Life Oasis International Church. The church does not assign ritual roles strictly by gender. There is a share leadership in the church. The church is headed by Rev Olusola Areogun while his wife Rev (Mrs) Oyenike Areogun serve alongside his husband as the senior Pastor. They both co host TV/Radio programs. In many of the conferences , they both participate in joint ministry ritual. The church operate an inclusive ministry where both men and women without rigid segregation participate and serve in complimentary role

Does the religious movement organise rituals for major life transitions?

ID: 10192

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply:

ID:
10193

- Baptism for adults
- Birth
- Death
- Marriage
- Ordination

Notes: The church organises programs for various ceremonies like marriage, child dedication and ministry ordination. During the wedding ritual, the couples receives the church blessings under the Pastoral oversight of Rev Olusola Areogun and Rev (Mrs) Oyenike Areogun. They incorporate

vow, prayer and communal celebrating of the union. In child dedication, the baby will be dedicated to God during the Congregational prayer. Also when ministry ordination takes place it involves the laying of hand , prophetic impartation and send forth for service.

↳ Does the ritual include a liminal phase, in which participants occupy an intermediate position between two social or spiritual states? ID: 10194

– Yes

Notes: This happens when individual steps forward confessing struggles and prayer for deliverance is offered. Also during ordination ritual when laying of hand and commissioning and send forth happens it is intermediate state between two social status or spiritual state

Is pilgrimage encouraged within the religious movement? ID: 10195

– No

Notes: Life Oasis International Church does not encouraged pilgrimage as a practice. The religious group focuses more on how people will encounter God through corporate worship , deliverance session and prophetic impartation. It however does not condemned anyone who feels like embarking on Christian pilgrimage

Does the religious movement encourage male and/or female circumcision? ID: 10196

– No

Notes: The church does not concern itself with circumcision. It is left for the prerogatives of the parents of a child or individual concerned as it has nothing to do with salvation

Does the religious movement practice body modifications? ID: 10208

– No

Notes: The religious group believes that body modifications does not change inner man. There the church does not do body modification. The focus is more on inner change which is believed will eventually reflects in the body.. The church believes that through encounter with God inner man will change and will later reflect on the outside. Changing of physical body when the inner is not change is not a real spiritual transformation

Do members regularly use crystals, herbs, alchemical products or spiritual tools? ID: 10213

– No

Notes: The church does not encouraged or get involved in such things. The church relies exclusively on prayer, scripture reading and laying of hands for healing and deliverance. The founder message on

Victory over witchcraft explicitly denounce charms, herbalism, ritual artifacts as demonic deception. He directed believers to shun those things and embrace the Holy Spirit alone

Do members have out-of-body experiences?

ID: 10217

– No

Notes: Out of the body experience is not part of the teaching of the group.. The Church only legalise Pentecostal experience which centres on Holy Spirit . The manifestation of the Holy Spirit like dream , prophecy, vision trance are the only experiences encouraged by the church

Does the religious movement practice divination or predict the future?

ID: 10219

– No

Notes: The church does not concern itself or encouraged such practices as divination and prediction of the future. The word of God is considered as having the final authority on what happens and on what to do

Does the religious movement self-describe as practising magic?

ID: 10221

– No

Notes: The religious body does not describe itself as practising magic, it does not believe or have faith in such believes. The church believes in Christian doctrine of Holy Spirit,baptism and spiritual authority of the bible

Does the religious movement practise death rituals?

ID:

– No

10223

Notes: The Life Oasis International Church does not practice death ritual. They however conduct a biblical memorial services which focused on hope and preaching eternal life through Christ rather than ceremonial rites or ancestor veneration or elaborate death custom

Are the religious movement's funeral and burial customs similar to those of the wider community?

ID:

– Yes

10226

Notes: The burial custom within the group is not different from the burial tradition as it is being done in other Pentecostal church

Is there anything important about ritual practices that has not been covered above? ID: 10227
If so, please describe it briefly.

– Specify: No

Notes: The needful on burial custom is covered

Individual Ritual Practices

Does the religious movement have ritual practices for individuals (e.g., prayer or meditation)? ID: 10228

– Yes

↳ What are the purposes of the individual ritual practices? ID: 10229

- Life benefits (e.g., health or happiness)
- Material benefits (e.g., wealth, property or promotion)
- Offer praise
- Patience
- Promote humility
- Protection
- Reaffirm commitment to the religious movement or supernatural power

Notes: The religious group encouraged members to have private devotion beyond Congregational devotion. To experience spiritual growth they are taught to engage in intimate prayer with God. Fasting is also encouraged to live above all odds. Spiritual exercise that will encouraged spiritual growth are taught as part of what will give them victory over life's challenges.. Moreover ways to live victorious life are part of the founders teaching. Personal Bible study and meditation in the Bible is seen as another way of aligning with God.

↳ Does the religious movement follow a set schedule for individual rituals? ID: 10230

– Other:: There is no rigid schedule of religious ritual for the members

Notes: Individuals are encouraged to develop a working relationship with God. Through this, personal conviction and devotion the believer will naturally engage in ritual activities that is pleasing to God.

↳ Is prayer emphasised as central to spiritual progress?

ID: 10231

– Yes

Notes: Prayer is strongly emphasised as it is central for spiritual growths. In the church there is always an all night prayer meeting for the stewards. Different stewards group meet at assigned day for their prayer. The church teachings portray prayer as the mechanism for all kind of successes. Is it breakthrough, dream realization, intimacy with God or becoming strong spiritually, personal prayer, praying in tongues are taught as foundational for it . To live a victorious life, prayer life must be cultivated.

– Yes

Notes: Prayer is strongly emphasised as it is central for spiritual growths. In the church there is always an all night prayer meeting for the stewards. Different stewards group meet at assigned day for their prayer. The church teachings portray prayer as the mechanism for all kind of successes. Is it breakthrough, dream realization, intimacy with God or becoming strong spiritually, personal prayer, praying in tongues are taught as foundational for it . To live a victorious life, prayer life must be cultivated.

– Yes

Notes: Prayer is strongly emphasised as it is central for spiritual growths. In the church there is always an all night prayer meeting for the stewards. Different stewards group meet at assigned day for their prayer. The church teachings portray prayer as the mechanism for all kind of successes. Is it breakthrough, dream realization, intimacy with God or becoming strong spiritually, personal prayer, praying in tongues are taught as foundational for it . To live a victorious life, prayer life must be cultivated. In the life Oasis International Church, corporate and private prayer are essential. Regular prayer chain, all night vigils like crossover night, annual school of ministry all integrate fervent prayer session in the programs. The church believes in the transformative power of prayer in aligning believers into God's will for their lives

↳ Is meditation emphasised as central to spiritual progress?

ID:
10232

– No

Notes: The church does not emphasise any kind of spiritual meditation apart from words of God. Prayer, speaking in tongues and commitment to words of God are encouraged. However meditating on Gods words is also considered to be good for believers.

Devotional Practices

Are there rituals that express devotion to supernatural beings?

ID: 10237

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 10238

- Devotion rituals are required of all members
- Devotion rituals are performed at set times or calendar dates
- Devotional rituals are conducted in groups
- Other:: Devotional rituals can be done anywhere as ordinary space can be transformed to sacred space while the permanent sacred space is the church

Notes: The church believes in trinitarian Godhead of the Father, Son and Holy Spirit. These supernatural are believed to be one. In Sunday services and conferences, praise song, corporate worship and prayer exalting Jesus as the saviour are features of the group.

↳ Are devotional rituals emphasised over other practices?

ID:
10239

– No

Notes: Devotional rituals are not emphasized over other practices . There is a balanced spiritual formation that the group emphasized

↳ Are dedicated spaces or places central to devotional practices?

ID: 10240

– No

Notes: Dedicated spaces or places are not central to devotional practices

↳ Are devotional practices directed toward self-transformation?

ID: 10245

– Yes

Notes: Devotional practices in the Life Oasis international church are directed towards self transformation

↳ Are altered states induced through devotional practice?

ID: 10246

– No

Notes: Such does not happen In the religious group

Are images of the divine permitted?

ID:
10247

– No

Notes: In the Dream centre of the Life Oasis International Church, use of image or praying through images are forbidden. The group hold on to worshipping in spirit and in truth. The group focuses on

spiritual realities than on using of icon or images. Such practices are regarded as idolatry

Is worship integrated into daily activities?

ID: 10251

– Yes

Notes: The Church teaches that worship should be a daily activities. The believers life should be a living sacrifice to God. Wherever a believer should stay, either at work, home, market or wherever, he should be a routine to worship God with his life

Do members feel or show gratitude to supernatural powers after receiving positive outcomes?

ID: 10252

– Yes

↳ On what occasions are gratitude expressed?

ID: 10253

- Avoiding injury or attack
- Childbirth
- Desired weather conditions
- Good harvest
- Healing
- Job promotion
- Lifting of curses or black magic
- Material blessings
- Protection from malevolent spiritual forces
- Success in person projects
- Safety during travel

Notes: Thanksgiving should be a lifetime action. Believers are to give thanksgiving to supreme being at all times

↳ Do members demonstrate gratitude through material offerings or sacrifices?

ID: 10254

– Yes

↳ Do members light candles or incense?

ID: 10255

– No

Notes: Member do not use candle

↳ Do members provide valuable/important goods (e.g., food, drinks, money, jewellery, etc.) to supernatural beings? ID: 10256

– No

Notes: These are not part of their practices. Members are not encouraged to bring in food or other valuable or jewellery but individual can decide on what to give to God or as he pleases

↳ Do members contribute time, money or effort to religious activities such as repairing places of worship? ID: 10257

– Yes

Notes: This is done on voluntary giving. The believers who wants to give is expected to do so voluntarily

↳ Do members participate in feasts/partying? ID: 10258

– Yes

Notes: The members as part of larger community participate in fellowship with one another and also support each other. They do participate in social activities

↳ Do members offer animal sacrifices? ID: 10259

– No

Notes: The members do not offer animal sacrifice as it is against the teaching of the group

↳ Do members offer human sacrifices? ID: 10260

– I Don't Know

Notes: No kind of sacrifice is required to be offered. No animal no human as Christ is believed to have made himself as the sacrifice needed. He has atoned for the believers

↳ Do members demonstrate gratitude through non-material expressions? ID: 10261

– Yes

- ↳ Do members offer prayers of thanksgiving? ID: 10262
 – Yes
 Notes: Prayer of thanksgiving is one of the acceptable sacrifice among the believers
- ↳ Do members use songs, dances or dramatic performances? ID: 10263
 – Yes
 Notes: Members use songs, dances to give thanksgiving
- ↳ Do members use emotional expressions, e.g., crying, submissive postures, raised hands, smiling/laughing etc.? ID: 10264
 – Yes
 Notes: Members do exercise their emotion when thanking God.
- ↳ Do members abstain from substances or practices (e.g., fasting)? ID: 10265
 – Yes
 Notes: Fasting and abstinence from certain actions are part of religious obligations expected from the believer
- ↳ Do members praise supernatural beings in public? ID: 10266
 – Yes
 Notes: Singing praises to God among the members is not restricted to anywhere. It can be done anywhere and anytime
- ↳ Do members use other non-material expressions? ID: 10267
 – Yes
 Notes: Members extensively used non material to praise God. This can come in form of spontaneous hallelujah, prophetic declaration and corporate singing
- ↳ Do members express gratitude through acts of prosociality? ID: 10269
 Prosociality refers to behaviors and attitudes intended to benefit others or society as a whole.
 – Yes

- ↳ Do members help third parties as acts of paying it forward? ID:10270
 – Yes
 Notes: Members do help third parties as an act of paying forward
- ↳ Do members promise to behave better (e.g., be more devout, honest, generous, etc.) in the future? ID: 10271
 – Yes
- ↳ Do members promise to do nice things for supernatural beings in the future? ID:10272
 – Yes
- ↳ Do members use other acts of prosociality? ID: 10273
 – Yes
 Notes: Anything that can benefit society and humanity at large is greatly encouraged within the religious movement

Transmission

- Does the religious movement organise spiritual retreats? ID:
 – Yes 10274
- ↳ Does the religious movement manage or own its own premises for spiritual retreats? ID:10275
 – Yes
 Notes: The religious group manages and own its own premises for its spiritual retreat.
- Is a teacher-student (i.e., guru-chela) relationship considered essential for spiritual progress? ID:10276
 – No
 Notes: In the Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church, a practice of a teacher -student (guru-chela) relationship considered essential for spiritual progress does not exist. The group utilize

congregational teaching methods where there is collective access to e scripture. This can be in a Sunday service, midweek Bible study or in other program.

Is there a line of succession that confirms who holds spiritual authority? ID: 10278

– No

Notes: The church does not have a formal line of succession that confirm who will hold spiritual authority. The current leadership has a family relate leadership. Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun as the General Overseer with his wife Rev. (Mrs) Oyenike Areogun as the senior Pastor and their children Pastor Joshua Areogun and Miss Peace Areogun are actively serving in the ministry.

Are stages of spiritual development acknowledged? ID: 10279

– Yes

↳ Do members move through formal stages or levels? ID: 10280

– Yes

↳ Does this resemble an educational syllabus? ID: 10281

– Yes

Notes: Members must complete a believers class which runs for 52 weeks

↳ Is there a pay structure to advance through formal stages or levels? ID: 10282

– No

Notes: It is free without any payment.

↳ Do members need to be formally initiated to receive advanced instruction? ID: 10285

– No

Notes: Anyone who wants to move to the next level will have to start attending some specialized training like "Men in Ministry" or "Women in Ministry"

Do members take vows to keep teachings secret? ID: 10288

– No

Notes: There is no such things as members taking vows to keep secret.

Do members believe that some knowledge can only be transmitted orally?

ID: 10289

– Yes

Notes: Members do believe that some knowledge can only be transmitted orally. There are core beliefs and knowledge which can be preached and testimonies which are transmitted orally. Even the teaching of the founder are extensively transmitted orally either through radio/TV or online platform

Do members believe that some knowledge can only be transmitted energetically?

ID: 10290

– No

Notes: Life Oasis International Church does not have any believed that some knowledge can only be transmitted energetically. Through preaching, Holy Spirit illumination and laying of hands in prayer, anointing can be transmitted. No secret knowledge is articulated in their practices

Do members believe that some knowledge can only be transmitted telepathically?

ID: 10291

– No

Notes: The concepts of telepathy are not part of the teaching of the religious group. It is therefore not expected to be present among the member. It is against the teaching of the group

Food and Drink

Are certain foods forbidden in the religious movement?

ID:

– No

10292

Notes: There is liberty to eat all kind of good food . The believe of the group follows Pentecostal belief declaring all food clean through Christ's authority

Are members discouraged or prohibited from eating with non-members?

ID: 10296

– No

Notes: Members are not discourage or prohibited from eating with non members. The teaching of the group encourage kingdom inclusivity of loving neighbour as oneself. The church manual encourage have right relationship with outsider to demonstrate the love of Christ

Are specific preparation methods required for food to be permitted?

ID: 10297

– No

Notes: There is no specific preparation methods required for food to be permitted

Are specific psychoactive substances forbidden (e.g., alcohol, nicotine, caffeine, or narcotics)? ID: 10299

– Yes

Notes: The group prohibit all form of psychoactive substances like alcohol, nicotine, caffeine, or narcotic. Members are required to abstain from them

Are members encouraged to use substances like alcohol, tobacco, or psychedelics during rituals? ID:10300

– No

Notes: Members are not allowed to use any substance anytime. Be it alcohol, tobacco psychedelics during or after rituals. All form of hard drinks are prohibited in the group

Is there anything important about food and drink that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID:10303

– Specify: There is none

Notes: All the necessary things about food are covered

Health and Healing

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: "Illness is a result of a moral failing." ID: 10304

– -2 Moderately opposed

Notes: The statement illness is a result of moral failing would be moderately opposed, this is because in the teaching of the founder Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun, illness is not always caused by personal sin. There are example in the bible when sickness is not as a result of sin. Notwithstanding, sin can as well be the cause of a sickness

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: "Illness is a result of karmic actions." ID:10305

– -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The religious group would strongly opposed the statement that illness is as a result of karmic action. The concept of karma is not part of Christian theology, it mainly comes from Hinduism and Buddhism where action in the past lives are believed to determine the present experience including illness and suffering. This totally goes against christian teachings of the Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International church

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10306
"Illness is a result of divine judgement."

– +1 Mildly endorsed

Notes: The statement that " illness is as a result of divine judgement" would be mildly agree because the teaching of the group stated that illness can come through several ways. It can come through judgement, it can come through conditions of the world, natural or medical condition, spiritual attack and situation for God to show his power

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10307
"Illness may be caused by supernatural forces."

– +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: The statement that "illness's may be caused by supernatural forces" will be moderately endorsed. This is because there is possibility of the supernatural influence in human life which can also cause sickness. Of course it is not the only supernatural that can cause illness . Biological factors, natural causes, environmental factors and so on can be the cause

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10308
"Medicine helps, but only God or the divine truly heals."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The group would strongly endorsed the statement that medicine help but only God can truly heals

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10309
"Abortion is always immoral."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: This will be strongly agreed that " abortion is always immoral" by the religious group

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID:10310
"Biomedical institutions are often harmful and immoral."

– -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: This group would strongly be opposed to the saying that "Biomedical institutions are often harmful and immoral". This is because medical knowledge is often considered as knowledge that emanated from God to cater for human body

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10311
"Biomedical interventions are helpful but incomplete."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The statement that "biomedical interventions are helpful but incomplete" would be strongly endorsed. This is because without God ultimate healing is impossible.

Does the religious movement offer healing or therapy to members? ID: 10312

– Yes

↳ What healing or therapy techniques are offered to members? ID:
10313

– Other: Religious and pastoral form of therapy

Notes: Religious and pastoral therapy may be special prayer for healing, deliverance, faith based support which can include counselling etc

↳ Are healing or therapy techniques offered for most physical maladies? ID:
10314

– Yes

Notes: This comes mainly in form of prayer while seeking for spiritual intervention. From minor to chronic illness prayers are offered for divine intervention

↳ Are healing or therapy techniques offered for most emotional maladies? ID: 10315

– Yes

Notes: Healing or therapy techniques are offered for emotional maladies

↳ Are healing or therapy techniques offered for most spiritual maladies? ID:
10316

– Yes

Notes: Healing or therapeutics are offered for the most spiritual maladies

↳ Are reports of miraculous healing common? ID: 10317

– Yes

Notes: There are reports of miraculous healing. This is usually considered as the act of God

↳ Do members sometimes rely only on prayer, meditation or alternative medicine instead of seeing a doctor? ID: 10318

– Yes

Notes: There are members who can sometimes rely only on prayer and their faith in what God can do instead of seeing doctor.

↳ Are members expected to pay for healing or therapy services? ID: 10319

– No

Notes: Members are not expected to pay as it is considered as part of w responsibility of the church. Notwithstanding voluntary donation is not discouraged

↳ Are donations expected? ID: 10321

– Yes

Notes: Freewill offering and donation are encouraged to be given by the members. Tithe and other freewill offering are to run the ministry

↳ Do members believe that healing energy can reach people who are far away? ID: 10322

– Yes

Notes: Members believed that healing can reach them not minding the distance.

↳ Can healing be done without the person's awareness? ID: 10323

– Yes

Notes: Members believed that healing can be done without e person's awareness. This is an act of God as God cannot be restricted . He can exercise His sovereignty

↳ Do healing or therapy techniques rely mainly on conversation? ID: 10324

– No

Notes: It does not necessarily mean without conversation healing cannot be done. Dialogue or conversation can occur during counseling however healing or therapy does not mainly rely on conversation

– Yes

- ↳ What healing or therapy techniques are offered to members? ID: 10313
 – Other:: Religious and pastoral form of therapy
 Notes: Religious and pastoral therapy may be special prayer for healing, deliverance, faith based support which can include counselling etc
- ↳ Are healing or therapy techniques offered for most physical maladies? ID: 10314
 – Yes
 Notes: Healing or therapy techniques are offered for the most physical maladies.
- ↳ Are healing or therapy techniques offered for most emotional maladies? ID: 10315
 – Yes
 Notes: Healing and therapy techniques are offered for emotional and psychological maladies. Through pastoral counseling, various kinds of emotional stress like fear, anxiety depression relationship challenge are addressed
- ↳ Are healing or therapy techniques offered for most spiritual maladies? ID: 10316
 – Yes
 Notes: Healing or therapy techniques are offered for the most spiritual maladies
- ↳ Are reports of miraculous healing common? ID: 10317
 – Yes
 Notes: There are report of miraculous act of God and Divine intervention.
- ↳ Do members sometimes rely only on prayer, meditation or alternative medicine instead of seeing a doctor? ID: 10318
 – Yes
 Notes: Members can sometimes rely only on prayer and meditation on God's words and their faith in God for healing
- ↳ Are members expected to pay for healing or therapy services? ID: 10319
 – No
 Notes: Members are not expected to pay for healing or therapy services. It is part of the church

responsibility Notwithstanding freewill or special donation are not discouraged

↳ Are donations expected? ID: 10321

– Yes

Notes: Freewill donation are accepted from the members.

↳ Do members believe that healing energy can reach people who are far away? ID: 10322

– Yes

Notes: Members believe that healing can reach people who are far away. God is conceived to be everywhere and can express his sovereign power as he likes

↳ Can healing be done without the person's awareness? ID: 10323

– Yes

Notes: Healing can be done without the person's awareness

↳ Do healing or therapy techniques rely mainly on conversation? ID: 10324

– No

Notes: Healing therapy does not rely mainly on conversation

– Yes

↳ What healing or therapy techniques are offered to members? ID: 10313

– Other:: Religious and pastoral form of therapy

Notes: Religious and pastoral therapy may be special prayer for healing, deliverance, faith based support which can include counselling etc

↳ Are healing or therapy techniques offered for most physical maladies? ID: 10314

– Yes

Notes: The kind of therapy being offered are regarded as spiritual support rather than medical treatment. The group does not give medical treatment

↳ Are healing or therapy techniques offered for most emotional maladies? ID: 10315

– Yes

Notes: In the religious group healing or therapeutics support is generally offered for emotional and psychological difficulties

↳ Are healing or therapy techniques offered for most spiritual maladies? ID: 10316

– Yes

Notes: The Church provide healing and therapy for spiritual maladies . Some spiritual therapy address feeling of spiritual emptiness, temptation and struggling with sins or bondage lack of direction in life

↳ Are reports of miraculous healing common? ID: 10317

– Yes

Notes: There are reports of miraculous in healing and deliverance through divine intervention

↳ Do members sometimes rely only on prayer, meditation or alternative medicine instead of seeing a doctor? ID: 10318

– Yes

Notes: Some concerned members may sometimes rely solely on prayer or meditation on God's words. The are teaching on faith by the founder where God is addressed as the ultimate healer

↳ Are members expected to pay for healing or therapy services? ID: 10319

– No

Notes: The members concerned are not expected to pay. Prayer for healing and deliverance are considered as the responsibility of the church. Notwithstanding voluntary giving or donation is not discouraged

↳ Are donations expected? ID: 10321

– Yes

Notes: Members are encouraged to give willingly. Freewill offering , tithe are expected from the members to support the church ministry

↳ Do members believe that healing energy can reach people who are far away? ID:

– Yes

10322

Notes: Members believe that healing or divine intervention can reach people who far away. Distance is not a barrier to power of God

↳ Can healing be done without the person's awareness?

ID: 10323

– Yes

Notes: Healing can be done without the person's awareness. This is believed as the act of God. It is not human action. This reveals what is called God sovereignty

↳ Do healing or therapy techniques rely mainly on conversation?

ID: 10324

– No

Notes: The healing or therapy techniques do not rely mainly on conversation. There may be counseling and dialogue as part of the process but it does not necessarily connote that without conversation prayer cannot be offered.

Is vaccination an important issue within the religious movement?

ID: 10325

– No

Notes: Vaccination is not an important issue within the religious group

Does the religious movement have special rules or beliefs about blood transfusions? ID: 10326

– No

Notes: There is no special rule or belief about blood transfusion entrenched in the practices of the group

Does the religious movement actively discourage or forbid any medicines, treatments or vaccinations?

ID: 10327

– No

Notes: The religious movement does not discourage or forbid any medicine treatment or vaccination

Are sick members ever excluded from the religious movement?

ID:

– No

10329

Notes: They usually pray for such members who are sick

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: ID:10330
"Euthanasia (i.e., deliberately killing those near the end of their lives or with terminal illnesses) is always immoral."

— -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The church would strongly opposed the concept of Euthanasia as they believe that its only God who can give life and who should take life

Does the religious movement have any beliefs or practices for people who are dying ID:
(e.g., palliative care)? 10331

— No

Notes: There is no special practice or believe for those who are dying. What the church does is to help them with prayer and give emotional support to those around them

Does the religious movement encourage the use of alternative or complementary ID: 10333
medicine or therapies?

— No

Notes: The church is neutral as it does not dictate on the health challenge or on what to use. However the church has always stands in prayer and emotional support for those who are sick

Does the religious movement have teachings or practices about female reproductive ID:10338
health, including menstruation, pregnancy, and childbirth?

— No

Notes: The Dream centre of the life Oasis International church does not have any teaching or practices about female reproductive health.

Does the religious movement believe in posthuman or transhuman transformation, ID:10339
whereby individuals can use technology to transcend human capabilities?

— No

Notes: The group does not believe in posthuman or transhuman transformation or the use of technology to transcend human capacity. The group believes in the Holy Spirit who empowers believers

Does the religious movement encourage or mandate physical exercise? ID:10343

— No

Notes: The group does not concern itself with exercise of any nature .

Does the religious movement encourage or mandate members to abstain from physical exercise? ID: 10347

– No

Notes: The religious group does not encourage or discourage members to either abstain or involve in physical exercise

Are specific genres of music prohibited or discouraged? ID: 10349

– No

Notes: The church does not concern itself much about the genre of music. However christian gospel music are prescribed for the believer

Does the religious movement have specific teachings or practices involving dance? ID: 10350

– No

Notes: There are no specific teaching or practices involving dance in the religious group

Does the religious movement promote ascetic disciplines, involving the restriction of desires, pleasures, or material attachments as a means of spiritual advancement? ID: 10354

– No

Notes: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church does not necessarily engage in ascetic discipline, restricting desires, pleasures or material attachments for spiritual advancement, they rather consider self discipline and restricting one's desires as part of their devotion to the God

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statement: "Suicide is always immoral." ID: 10362

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church would strongly endorsed that "Suicide is immoral" The biblical sanctity of life is uphold by the group. Suicide is greatly rejected in the group

Has anyone ended their life for religious or ideological reasons to advance the goals of the religious movement? ID: 10363

– No

Notes: In the Dream centre of the Life Oasis International Church there is no one who has ended his life for the sake of the religious group. The only sacrifice acknowledged by the group is the atoning death of Jesus Christ

Is there anything important about health and healing that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly.

ID: 10364

– Specify: There is nothing important about health that has not been covered

Gender and Sexuality

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10365
"There are two distinct genders."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: There are two distinct gender would be strongly endorsed. The biblical teaching that God created them male and female are accepted in the church

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10366
"Gender is a social construct."

– -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: Gender is a social construct would strongly be opposed. The Church Life Oasis International Church affirms biblical theology of male and female.

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10367
"Men and women are equal."

– +2 Moderately endorsed

Notes: The statement that men and women are equal would moderately be accepted. Men and women are equal in value before God but are given different roles or responsibility

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10368
"Men are naturally superior to women."

– -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The statement that "men are naturally superior to women" would be opposed in the religious group. The teaching of the founder Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun emphasized equal value and dignity of men and women before God. The church claim equality in creation of male and female, spiritual equality but role distinction

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10369
"Women are naturally superior to men."

– -3 Strongly opposed

Notes: The statement that "women are naturally superior to men" would be strongly opposed. The teaching in the group emphasised equality in creation

To what extent would the religious movement agree with the following statements: ID: 10370
"Men have a responsibility to care for women and children."

– +3 Strongly endorsed

Notes: The statement " Men have a responsibility to care for the women and children " would be strongly endorsed. The family structure which give the responsibilities of man to be a provider and protector is emphasised in the church

How many genders are recognised? ID: 10371

– Two (man and woman)

Notes: Male and female gender are recognised by the church

How does the religious movement view gender relations? ID: 10372

– Distinct and opposite social roles for men and women (complementary and equal)

Notes: The church view the gender relations in distinct and complementary social roles for men and women. Both are equal but have a distinct role that complement each other

Is transcending gender viewed as a spiritual ideal? ID: 10373

– No

Notes: The church Life Oasis International Church teaching follows conservative Pentecostal Christian teaching, "transcending gender as a spiritual ideal" would be strongly opposed

Does the theology allow equal access to leadership for all genders? ID: 10374

– No

Notes: The theology allows for male and female gender leadership. Rev Olusola Ayodele Areogun is the current General Overseer and his wife is the senior Pastor. However, beside male and female the group does not recognise other gender as it uphold conservative Pentecostal teaching

Is decision-making equally shared among genders? ID:

– No

10376

Notes: Decision making is done at the level of the top leadership . It is considered to be partly shared between the two recognised. gender male and female

Do men and women follow different paths to spiritual advancement?

ID: 10377

– No

Notes: In Life Oasis International Church both men and women follow e same spiritual path toward salvation and growth .There may be specific roles yet thesame part must be taken for spiritual advancement

Are there distinct roles for transgender, non-binary, genderfluid, genderqueer, asexual, third gender or androgynous members?

ID:
10378

– No

Notes: There are no roles for transgender, non binary, gender fluid , genderqueer, asexual , third gender or androgynous members. The church uphold a conservative Pentecostal tradition

Is religious instruction gender-segregated?

ID:
10379

– No

Notes: Religious instruction within the group is not gender segregated. There may be gender specific classes yet the instruction are the same

Do men and women participate separately in certain rituals?

ID: 10380

– No

Notes: Both gender participate in most ritual altogether. There can be exception in some instances when gender specific programs may be held.

Are there male-only social spaces?

ID:
10381

– No

Notes: The church does not maintain only male social spaces. It maintains a mixed social spaces

Are there female-only social spaces?

ID: 10382

– No

Notes: The church maintain mixed gender social space

Are there specific behavioural roles assigned to each gender (or agender) within the religious movement? ID: 10383

– No

Notes: There are no specific behavioural roles assigned to each gender

Can members express gender in flexible or playful ways? ID: 10390

– No

Notes: The idea is not accepted in the religious group.

– No

Notes: The idea is not accepted in the religious group.

Is gender-inclusive language used in the religious movement's teachings or practices? ID: 10391

– No

Notes: The gender inclusive language is not used in the religious teachings. The group maintain conservative christian practices. It only factor in male and female

Does the religious movement have specific teachings about marriage or partnerships? ID: 10392

– Yes

↳ Are in-movement partnerships or marriages strongly encouraged? ID: 10393

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 10394

– Monogamous marriage between members

Notes: Monogamous marriage among members are encouraged

↳ Does the religious movement urge members to divorce non-believing spouses? ID: 10395

– No

Notes: The church does not encouraged or urge members to divorce non believing members

↳ Does the religious movement encourage members to marry or formally partner each other? ID: 10396

– Yes

↳ Select all attitudes that apply to pre-marital sex. ID: 10397

– Forbidden

– Discouraged

Notes: Pre-sex are prohibited

↳ Are there explicit rules about who may marry whom? ID: 10398

– Yes

↳ Are men allowed to marry outside of the religious movement? ID: 10399

– Yes

Notes: Men can marry from outs

↳ Are women allowed to marry outside of the religious movement? ID: 10400

– Yes

Notes: They are allowed to marry outside the religious movement.

↳ Does the religious movement define marriage as exclusively heterosexual? ID: 10401

– Yes

Notes: It is exclusively heterouse

↳ Are homosexual partnerships officially recognised? ID: 10402

– No

Notes: Homosexuality partnership is officially prohibited

↳ Is marriage to more than one person allowed for men? ID: 10403
– No

Notes: Marriage to more than one person is not allowed

↳ Is marriage to more than one person allowed for women? ID: 10404
– No

Notes: Marriage to more than one person for women is not allowed

↳ Is marriage to minors allowed? ID: 10405
– No

Notes: Marriage to a minor is prohibited

↳ Does leadership regulate partner selection? ID: 10406
– No

Notes: Persona Choice prevail in marriage partner selection

↳ Are marriage partners selected by parents? ID: 10407
– No

Notes: Partner are not selected by parent. It is the sole responsibilities of the partner involved

Does the religious movement have teachings about sexuality? ID: 10408
– Yes

↳ Is celibacy required or encouraged for certain members? ID: 10409
– No

Notes: Celibacy is not required for any member

↳ Are sexual conduct standards different for men and women? ID: 10411

– No

Notes: Sexual conduct standards applies to both male and female

↳ Is homosexual activity explicitly prohibited? ID: 10414

– Yes

Notes: Homosexual activity is explicitly prohibited

↳ Are sexual practices within the movement linked to specific rituals or ceremonies? ID: 10415

– No

Notes: Sexual practices are not linked to any specific ritual or ceremony. Sexual practices is rather a matter of marital exclusive right. Sex is limited to marriage

↳ Are there theological reasons for sexual relationships between leaders and members? ID: 10417

– No

Notes: Life Oasis International Church does not provide any theological reasons permitting sexual relationship between leaders and member. It does not permit such and its condemnable act in the group

↳ Are sexual thoughts and behaviours addressed through ritual confession or guidance sessions? ID: 10419

– Yes

↳ Are sexual fantasies considered sinful or shameful? ID: 10420

– Yes

Notes: Sexual fantasies are considered sinful and shameful as long as you are not married

↳ Is sexual promiscuity considered sinful or shameful? ID: 10421

– Yes

Notes: Sexual promiscuity is considered sinful and shameful

↳ Are there specific rituals for sexual purification? ID: 10422
– No

Notes: Life Oasis does not proffer specific purification. Individual concern will have to repent, pray and fast to be delivered from sexual sin

↳ Are the religious movement's sexual practices kept secret from outsiders? ID: 10423
– No

Notes: The religious group does not keep sexual practices secret from the outsider

↳ Are the religious movement's sexual practices at tension with mainstream conventions? ID: 10424
– No

Notes: The religious group sexual practices may not necessarily be in tension with some Pentecostal practices.

Are there teachings about LGBTQI+ identity? ID: 10425

– No

Notes: The church does not have teaching about LGBTQI+identity

Is there anything important about gender and sexuality that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 10427

– Specify: There is nothing important about gender that has not been covered

Financial Practices

Are you able to provide information about the financial practices of the religious movement? ID: 10428

– No

Notes: The information about the financial practices are not readily available. However the church emphasized financial obligation of the members to the church. Tithing, offerings and benevolence giving are some of the financial practices of the church. 10percent plus freewill offering are used to fund Ministry expansion, Pastoral support and kingdom project.

Can an estimate be made of the movement's total financial size (e.g., assets or annual income)? ID: 10437

— No

Notes: This is not readily available and the information of such are privately kept away from the public. Unlike in some country of the world, Nigeria government does not mandate religious group to publicly give their financial reporting and their is no sanction in that regards

Does the religious movement operate its own economic system as an alternative to the wider economy? ID: 10438

This includes three aspects: 1) Semi-autonomous financial spheres, such as cooperative enterprises, internal currencies, or communal resource-sharing. 2) Ethical or spiritual economies, replacing profit motives with service, reciprocity, or purity principles. And 3) parallel systems, such as member-run businesses, microcredit schemes, or barter networks.

— No

Notes: The Life Oasis International Church does not operate it's own alternative economy. The church relies on tithe, freewill offering and donations for it's operation

Are members required to give up personal assets and fully commit to communal finances? ID: 10439

— No

Notes: There is no such practices as given up personal assets and fully commit to communal finances. Members are taught on how to live right and achieve their God's given goal in life

To what extent would an average member describe themselves as "just getting by" financially? ID: 10441

— +1 Very well

Notes: They will surely agreed they are not backward . The teaching of the ministry promote prosperity and well being. Positive confession is also very key . Definitely they with confess to getting well financially

To what extent do members feel unable to afford basic necessities? ID: 10442

Basic necessities include accommodation, food and utilities.

— -2 Not at all

Notes: Members are able to afford basic things of life

To what extent do members feel unable to afford the things they want?

ID: 10443

Desirable goods may include clothes, leisure items and pleasurable activities.

– -2 Not at all

Notes: There no such things, members are able to afford what they want

To what extent are members likely be able to absorb an unexpected financial shock? ID: 10444

An unexpected financial shock often coincides with life events (e.g., divorce, loss of job, illness, bereavement, natural disasters or unexpected car repairs).

– 0 Unclear views, neutral

Notes: This may be difficult to give a definite answer.

To what extent are members likely to have money left over at the end of the month? ID:

10445

– -2 Not at all

Notes: This may depend on the financial stand of individual member. Yet they should be able to have money left

To what extent are members likely feel their life choices are limited by their financial situation? ID: 10446

– 0 Unclear views, neutral

Notes: This may depend on choice and what individual want in life . This may be difficult to decide

Is paying for spiritual or religious courses required for advancement?

ID: 10447

– No

Notes: There is no such things

Are members typically required to purchase books, materials, spiritual items or spiritual teachings sold by the religious movement?

ID: 10451

– Yes

Notes: Though it is not compulsory yet members are encouraged to buy the materials like books of the founder

Are members encouraged to sell materials owned or copyrighted by the religious

ID: 10452

movement?

– No

Notes: They are not enforced to sell the religious materials of the church. However there is a bookshop where members can voluntarily buy books in the church

Does the religious movement offer certification for spiritual practices it has developed?

ID:
10453

– No

Notes: There is no external certification for the program that the religious group has developed

Do members usually pay for spiritual services (e.g., consultations, blessings, healings or spiritual life activations)?

ID: 10457

– No

Notes: Members do not pay for spiritual services like consultation, blessings, healing or other spiritual ministrations.

Are members charged attendance fees for workshops, worship services, ceremonies, rituals or other spiritual events?

ID:
10458

– Yes

Notes: There are payment for certain programs like workshop, special training and other special event. However payment are not made for worship service except freewill offering during such program

Are members encouraged to use businesses run by other members or leaders within the religious movement?

ID:
10459

– No

Notes: Members are not encouraged to use businesses run by other members or leader within the religious group

Are luxury items for leaders purchased by the religious movement or donated by members?

ID:
10461

– No

Notes: The group or members are not in most cases responsible for the luxurious item for e leaders. Some of the luxurious item can come from individual voluntarily give or offer such as gift

Is internal employment or ordination considered more ethical than working outside the religious movement? ID: 10462

– Yes

Notes: To a member who is an insider, it will be yes but to outsider it will come with a different opinion

Are members encouraged to make financially risky choices in pursuit of a more spiritually valued life? ID: 10463

– No

Notes: Members are encouraged to live by faith and trust God for help. Notwithstanding, they do not encouraged members to get into debt or make financial mistake

Is earning substantial income viewed as important or spiritually beneficial? ID: 10464

– Yes

Notes: To earning substantial income is viewed as spiritually beneficial

Is entrepreneurship viewed as important? ID:

Entrepreneurship is the process of starting and running a new business. ID: 10465

– Yes

↳ Are members encouraged to establish spiritually or ethically oriented businesses? ID: 10466

– Yes

Notes: Members are encouraged to do business

↳ Are spiritually or ethically oriented businesses run by members financially independent from the religious movement (i.e., profits are not shared or paid as fees to the organisation)? ID: 10467

– Yes

Notes: There are business owners in the church

↳ Are members encouraged to develop personal brands that reflect their personality, personal skills or spiritual attainment? ID: 10468

– Yes

Notes: Member are encouraged to become business owners

↳ Are members encouraged to become influencers on social media? ID: 10469

– Yes

Notes: People can do business that suit their calling

↳ Does the religious movement offer courses on marketing, branding or advertising? ID: 10470

– No

Notes: There is no such training in the church

↳ Does income flow upward from income-generating members to higher leadership, similar to a multi-level marketing (MLM) model? ID: 10472

– No

Notes: Individual with private business runs his business outside of the religious group

Does the religious movement encourage donations? ID: 10473

– Yes

↳ How often are members asked or expected to contribute financially? ID: 10474

– Other:: As the need arise

Notes: There are various contributions. For project, special program and as the need arise

↳ Do members believe that generosity or donations result in greater personal prosperity? ID: 10477

– Yes

Notes: Since the contribution is labelled to be for God's work, members gives generously

↳ Are appeals for donations regularly made in emotionally charged or rousing settings? ID: 10478

– No

Notes: The appeal for donations are often made with specific need in view . Members are made to realise the need for them to give

↳ Does the religious movement track or record individual members' donations or tithes? ID: 10480

– Yes

Notes: The religious group does track individual members donation or tithe

↳ Is shame ever used to encourage or increase donations? ID: 10481

– No

Notes: They do not use shame strategies to collect donation from members. However giving and donation to the work of God are often tied to the supernatural who will bless you when you give

↳ Are individuals encouraged to make financial commitments to the religious movement based on aspirations rather than present financial means? ID: 10483

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 10484

– Act of faith or sacrifice

– As a test of spiritual commitment

– To receive material blessings or miracles

– As a mission to support the expansion of the religious movement

Notes: Members are encouraged to give to give as all they have are given to them by God

↳ Are members encouraged to make financial donations for specific project or causes? ID: 10485

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply: ID: 10486

– Emergency funds for natural disasters, ill health or misfortune (for members)

- Emergency funds for natural disasters, ill health or misfortune (for non-members)
- Charitable causes unrelate to the religious movement
- Missionary or outreach activities
- Temple building, building repairs or building of other institutional structures

Notes: Members are encouraged to give or donate toward specific needs

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 10486

- Emergency funds for natural disasters, ill health or misfortune (for members)
- Emergency funds for natural disasters, ill health or misfortune (for non-members)
- Charitable causes unrelate to the religious movement
- Missionary or outreach activities
- Temple building, building repairs or building of other institutional structures

Notes: Members are encouraged to give or donate toward specific needs

Are members experiencing financial hardship viewed as morally inferior or responsible for their situation (e.g., due to bad karma, weak faith, or insufficient spiritual investment)?

ID:
10487

– No

Notes: Members who are experiencing financial hardship are in most cases not viewed as morally inferior or responsible for their lot. However they can be challenged to do something with their situation either through prayer, and effort that can make things better for them

Does the religious movement encourage members to support other members who are struggling financially?

ID: 10488

– Yes

↳ Select all that apply:

ID: 10489

- Direct financial support to members by the religious movement
- Direct financial support between members

- Material support (e.g., housing, meals, childcare, or household assistance)
- Social support (e.g., job offers, employment opportunities, or professional networking)

Notes: The religious group does support their members through various form.

Are members ever encouraged to make personal donations that could reduce their financial independence or affect their dependents' inheritance? ID: 10490

– No

Notes: Member of the group are not encouraged to make personal donation that would reduce their inheritance independence or affect their dependents' inheritance.

Are members encouraged to work for the religious movement as unpaid volunteers? ID: 10491

– Yes

↳ On what basis do members participate in unpaid volunteering? ID: 10492

- Other: As those who believe in the vision of the leader

Notes: People who volunteer to work as unpaid worker has something else that they are doing. They do so because the believe in the vision of the leader

↳ Does the time spent on unpaid volunteer work limit members' ability to earn an income outside of the religious movement? ID: 10493

– No

Does the religious movement offer investment advice, loans, financial schemes, or financial products exclusively for members? ID: 10494

– No

Notes: The dream center of the life Oasis does not offer professional advise on loans, financial scheme or financial product for any member

Is there anything important about financial practices that have not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly. ID: 10498

– Specify: There is nothing to be covered again about financial practices

Is there anything important about practices that has not been covered above? If so, please describe it briefly.

ID:
10186

– Specify: There is nothing about practices that is yet to be covered

Legal Issues

Legal Status

Is this religious movement involved in legal issues/cases?

ID: 10499

– No

Notes: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church has no evidence or involvement with legal issues

Have there been any legal cases against the religious movement?

ID:
10500

– No

Notes: The church is not battling with any litigation.

Criminal Cases

Has the state initiated any criminal cases against the religious movement or its members?

ID:
10501

– No

Notes: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church has never been charge to court by the state for any wrong doing. The religious group enjoys harmony with the state government

Regulatory Cases

Have there been any other court cases against the religious movement for breaking laws or regulations?

ID: 10521

– No

Notes: There is no court case against the religious group for any kind of breaking law or regulations

Civil Cases Against the Movement

Have there been any civil cases against the religious movement or its members where financial compensation was sought? ID: 11412

– No

Notes: There have been no civil case against Life Oasis International Church or its member seeking financial compensation

Movement-Initiated Cases

Have any legal cases been started by the religious movement? ID: 10526

– No

Notes: Life Oasis International Church has not initiated any known legal case. Pentecostal practice employed spiritual warfare through prayer rather legal battles

Have any legal cases been threatened (but not formally initiated) by the religious movement? ID: 10531

– No

Notes: They may have been a threatened attempt but was not brought to limelight. On the record however there is no legal case against the group

Have there been any civil cases where the religious movement or one of its members filed a lawsuit against someone else? ID: 10532

– No

Notes: There is no known case where the the religious body or member filed a lawsuit against someone

Family Law

Have there been any family law cases, such as divorce, child custody, adoption, or spousal support, where the beliefs and practices of the religious movement were an important part of the case? ID: 10513

– No

Notes: There has not been any family law cases such as divorce, child custody, adoption or spousal support where the beliefs and practices of religious movement were important part of the case.

Have there been any family law cases initiated by a member, such as divorce, child custody, adoption, or spousal support, where the beliefs and practices of the religious movement were an important part of the case? ID: 10535

– No

Notes: There have been no family cases initiated by members where such things happened. The church has strategically position itself that member are taught and indoctrinated that you cannot take your challenge to the unbeliever but to believers who will help in guiding your decision. Also before you become a full member you must have gone through various teaching of the church. Till date there have not been a court case initiated by the member

Rights and Freedoms

Have the religious movement or any of its members started legal cases about freedom of religion or the exercise of religious or human rights? ID: 10542

– No

Notes: There is no member who started a legal case about freedom of religion or human right. The church itself has also advocated freedom for people and also engage in prayer warfare for people. Spiritual solution are sought even for people who may be thought to be under spiritual or oppression through fasting and prayer

Allegations of Harm to Members

Are there claims that the religious movement has interfered with investigations meant to prevent harm? ID: 10546

– No

Notes: There is no known case of claim or allegations that the religious movement has interfered with its investigation to prevent harm

Are there claims that the religious movement has engaged in coercive control of its members? ID: 10547

Coercive control entails an act or a pattern of acts of assault, threats, humiliation and intimidation or other abuse that is used to harm, punish, or frighten a victim. This includes behaviours designed to dominate, isolate and control another person. It can involve physical, emotional, financial or spiritual elements.

– No

Notes: There are no claim that the religious group has engaged in coercive control of its member

Are there claims that the religious movement has engaged in other potentially criminal offences that have not resulted in court proceedings? ID: 10548

– No

Notes: There are no record or claim that the religious movement has engaged in other potentially criminal offences that resulted in court proceeding

Has the religious movement made any reports or statements in response to accusations of wrongdoing? ID: 10551

– No

Notes: The religious movement has never made any statement or response to any accusation of wrongdoing

Has the religious movement changed any of its practices or teachings because of allegations of harm? ID: 10560

– No

Notes: The church has never change any of it's practices or teaching because of any allegation of harm

Does the religious movement have established procedures for safeguarding and protecting whistle-blowers? ID: 10558

– No

Notes: Life Oasis International Church does not have formal procedure for safe guarding and protecting whistle-blowers. However the indoctrination of the members not to respond to the issues and affairs of the church is well entrenched. Members are taught not to respond to issue of the church as it is the responsibility of the pastor. There are unofficial system in place that route everything to the command of the leadership of the church. The members are well grounded to defend the leaders in all front.

Have whistle-blower reports caused major changes within the religious movement? ID: 10559

– No

Notes: There are no such attempt of whistle-blower report that cause any change within the religious group

Libel and Slander

Has the religious movement sued for libel, defamation or slander? ID: 10552

– No

Notes: The Dream Centre of the Life Oasis International Church has never been sued for libel, defamation or slander

Is there anything important about legal cases that have not been covered above? If so, ID: 10561 please describe it briefly.

– Specify: There is no legal case that is yet to be addressed

Bibliography

General References

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